

***Rhizobium* inoculation, Phosphorus Fertilization, and Vermicompost
Application Impact on the Estimate of BNF and Productivity of Haricot bean
(*Phaseolus vulgaris L.*) and Selected Soil Properties at Dore Baffano Woreda,
Sidama Region**

MSc Thesis

SENAIT SHIMELS

HAWASSA UNIVERSITY

College of Agriculture

Hawassa, Ethiopia

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Sidama Region**

SENAIT SHIMELS

ADVISOR: SHIMELS GIZACHEW (Ph.D.)

CO-ADVISOR: ALEMAYEHU KIFLU (Ph.D.)

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October, 2023

DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated to my beloved and esteemed family

STATEMENT OF THE AUTHOR

I, Senait Shimels hereby declare that, this thesis is my genuine work, and that all sources of materials used for this thesis have been profoundly acknowledged. I solemnly declare that this thesis is not submitted to any other institution anywhere for the award of any academic degree, diploma or certificate.

Name: Senait Shimels

Signature: _____

Place: College of Agriculture, Hawassa University, Hawassa

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ANOVA	Analysis of variance
BNF	Biological Nitrogen Fixation
CEC	Cation Exchange Capacity
CSA	Central Statistical Agency
FAO	Food and Agricultural Organization
HSW	Hundred Seed Weight
LAI	Leaf Area Index
LSD	Least Significant Difference
m.a.s.l	Meters Above Sea Level
NDFA	Nitrogen derived from the atmosphere
OC	Organic Carbon
RCRD	Randomized Complete Block Design
SAS	Statistical Analysis Software
SNNPR	South Nation and Nationalities Peoples Region
TN	Total Nitrogen
VC	Vermi-compost

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ABSTRACT

*Haricot bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) is one of the major leguminous crops grown in Ethiopia. The potential yield of haricot beans is low due to low soil fertility and inadequate nutrient supply. A field experiment was conducted to evaluate the effect of rhizobium inoculation, phosphorus rate, and VC application on the estimate of BNF, improvement of soil fertility, and on the growth and yield of haricot bean at Dore baffano, Sidama region, from June to October 2021. A factorial combination of 2 levels of rhizobium (inoculated and un-inoculated) with 3 levels of phosphorus (0, 30, and 60 kg ha⁻¹) and VC (0, 2.5, and 5 t ha⁻¹) was laid in Randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications. All the relevant soil and Haricot bean growth and yield parameters were collected and computed using SAS software as well treatment means were compared using LSD at 5% probability. The Analysis of variance on the estimate of BNF, yield and yield components, soil moisture status, and soil chemical properties showed mixed effects. The soil analysis results revealed that inoculation with 5tha⁻¹ VC application increased the moisture status of soil at different growth stages and improved selected soil fertility parameters (TN, available P, %OC, CEC, and exc.K) after harvest. In addition, the interaction effect of phosphorus with VC application increased %OC, CEC, and available phosphorus in the soil. The interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with phosphorus rate, rhizobium inoculation with VC application, and phosphorus with VC application significantly affected % Ndfa, growth, and yield parameters of haricot bean. The highest %Ndfa (52.46%), branch number (4.87), pod number (19.60), above-ground dry biomass (3971kg ha⁻¹), and grain yield (2145kg ha⁻¹) were obtained from the interaction effect of 30kg ha⁻¹ P and 5tha⁻¹ VC, however, the interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with phosphorus rate and VC application significantly affects days to 50% flowering, days to 90% physiological maturity, seed number per pod and HSW, the highest seed number per pod (6.2) and HSW (29.83) was obtained from rhizobium inoculation with 30kg ha⁻¹ P and 5tha⁻¹ VC, in addition, the highest net benefit (60,986 ETB ha⁻¹) from the economic analysis was obtained due to this interaction effect. Therefore, the integrated application of rhizobium inoculation with 30kg ha⁻¹ P and 5tha⁻¹ VC is recommended in the area of Dore baffano to boost the fertility of the soil, the productivity of the haricot bean, and its economic profitability.*

Keywords: BNF, Haricot bean, Rhizobium, Vermicompost, phosphorus fertilization

1. INTRODUCTION

Agricultural lands are highly influenced by rapid population Growth in developing countries of Asia and Africa (Maisonet-guzman, 2011). By 2050, agricultural land is expected to decrease from 0.2- 0.1ha per capital in developing countries (FAO, 2015). Most smallholder farmers in developing countries utilize their agricultural lands beyond their production capacity which leads to a serious impact on soil fertility reduction and causes annual crop yield loss of 33.7 million tons globally (Panagos *et al.*, 2020).

The severity of soil degradation among different regions of Ethiopia has been increasing highly year to year (Alemayehu, 2020). About 2 billion cubic meters top soil is lost annually with important plant nutrients (Tsegaye, 2019). According to Zelleke *et al.* (2010), this might be caused due to soil erosion, poor soil management, and lack of proper organic fertilizer application. Different researches have been conducted on the rehabilitation of degraded soil and on how to utilize small farm areas in a sustainable manner (Clarke *et al.*, 2017), through different soil water conservation systems (Haile *et al.*, 2006), and improved soil fertility management (Zerssa *et al.*, 2021).

The use of legumes in cropping systems is an important practice to improve the fertility of depleted soils. Soil fertility under the production of legumes shows a positive impact in many legume-producing areas (Basalingappa, 2018), due to atmospheric N₂ fixation by rhizobium bacteria. Rhizobia are a large number of bacterial species that are able to fix atmospheric N₂ through symbiotic relationships with the roots of legume plants (Redmon and Smith, 2004). The reduction of atmospheric (N₂) to ammonia (NH₃) through Biological N fixation (BNF) is done by the nitrogenase enzyme, which is found only in prokaryotes (Bottomley and Myrold, 2015). Many N₂-fixing prokaryotes are di-azotrophic, which means that they can grow using atmospheric N₂ as their sole source of N while other organisms can fix N₂ only in symbiosis with another eukaryotic organism (Wagner, 2011). Symbiotic association between these N₂ fixing organisms and roots of legumes form special organs called nodules where N fixation occurs (Buraka, 2019).

In addition to atmospheric N₂ fixing capacity, grain legumes are important for human nutrition and health, animal fodder, soil fertility improvement, soil erosion reduction, and for increasing household revenue (Atnaf *et al.*, 2015). Next to cereals, grain legumes are the second most important crop in Ethiopia (Henry *et al.*, 2018). Faba beans, haricot beans, field peas and chickpeas are the four leading legumes in grain yield as well as in the area of production among grain legume species that grow in Ethiopia (Kebede, 2020). Among the four leading legumes, the haricot bean grows in the lowland and mid-altitudes of the country as the other three legumes grow in highland areas (Murut *et al.*, 2014).

Haricot bean is the most important pulse crop grown in central, southern, eastern and western Ethiopia (Bekele *et al.*, 2019), with Oromia, Amhara and Southern Nations Nationalities and Peoples Region (SNNPR) being the major producing regions (Worku, 2015). Local farmers of SNNPR use haricot bean as a readily available source of protein and it is high in calorie content (Worku, 2015; Henry *et al.*, 2018). However, the legume demand of Ethiopia by 2050 is expected to be highest with the rapid population growth being the major factor, due to this the self-sufficiency ratio of Ethiopia is lower in legumes compared to Kenya and Tanzania which had a higher self-sufficiency ratio in legumes (Deng *et al.*, 2018).

Several studies have confirmed that leguminous crops show remarkable growth and yield response to rhizobia inoculations in different agro-ecologies of Ethiopia (Adissie *et al.*, 2020; Gebrehana and Dagnaw, 2020). Rhizobia inoculants coated on legume seeds help to increase the rhizobia population around the roots of legumes (Hussain, 2017) and enhance the growth and yield of the legume crop (Kellman, 2008).

Rhizobium inoculants are selected strains of laboratory-cultured beneficial soil microorganisms, which are environmental friendly sources of nitrogen. These inoculants can improve and sustain soil fertility and soil health when used as part of a long-term rotation system (Argaw and Akuma, 2015). Moreover, they provide nitrogen and organic carbon for associated or subsequent crops.

In recent years, rhizobium inoculation becomes a significant technology for improving soil fertility and productivity in Ethiopia, along with chemical fertilizer (Genetu *et al.*, 2021). An experiment by Samago *et al.*, (2018) in Southern Ethiopia on haricot bean inoculation along

with P fertilization resulted in high grain yield. P is an important nutrient in promoting energy transfer to root nodules for efficient nitrogen fixation, to enhance root growth and to obtain higher grain yield (Genetu *et al.*, 2021). However, most soils in the world as well as in Ethiopia are P –deficient (Cordell, 2010;). This might be because P can precipitate easily with iron and aluminum in highland soils (Melese *et al.*, 2015) or by calcium in lowland soils. Although Al plays a significant role in P precipitation at temperate soils (Brenner *et al.*, 2019), available P can also be lost from the soil due to soil erosion where erosion flushes out P from agricultural soil to water bodies.

P fertilization increases the grain yield of legume crops (Gabisa *et al.*, 2017). Mebrahtu and Teklay, (2021) reported that low N₂-fixation is sometimes associated with low levels of P in the soil. P deficiency reduces nitrogen fixation which results in reduced growth and yield of legumes. In SNNPR of Ethiopia, the production of haricot beans without additional P is much lower (Gidago *et al.*, 2011). Thus the scarcity of this essential element results in poor haricot bean production as it is the highly required nutrient by this crop for effective growth and yield (Samago *et al.*, 2018).

Organic fertilizers are known for their capacity to improve crop production by providing important plant nutrients and enhancing soil physical, chemical, and biological properties (Bhattacharjee and Dey, 2014). Vermicompost is one of well stabilized, organic fertilizer with a low bulk density, high porosity and moisture holding capacity and high humus content (Asrin *et al.*, 2019) and has low C: N ratio which is favorable for microbial activity and further decomposition of Organic materials (Chanu *et al.*, 2018).

Vermicompost contains micro-sites rich in available carbon, nitrogen, and water-soluble P and often contain higher potassium than the surrounding soil (Argaw and Mnalku, 2017). Also, it promotes nitrogenase activity in the soil rhizosphere which helps nitrogen fixation in legume plants (Lazcano and Domínguez, 2011). In addition, the enzyme phosphatase which is present in vermicompost increases P availability to plants (Kumar and Kumar, 2017; Demir, 2019).

1.1. Statement of the problem

Haricot bean is a grain legume commonly grown in Sidama region, in the woreda of Dore Baffano, where the study was conducted. Farmers produce this crop commonly and consume in traditional dishes which serves as a source of protein to supplement the protein-deficient main dishes like maize and Enset (Gidago *et al.*, 2011) and is also a cash crop. However the production of this crop in most case is low (below its production capacity) due to several aspects. Thus, poor agricultural land managements are one of the major factors for declining soil fertility and crop productivity. In order to alleviate these problems, environmental friendly, easily applicable, long-lasting effect and reliable technology like rhizobium inoculation and vermicompost application need to be adopted in the Agricultural sector. However, the process of nitrogen fixation is sensitive to P deficiency (Hussain, 2017). This is because it plays an important role in N cycling as adenosine tri-phosphate is required in large quantities for legumes to undergo N₂ -fixation (Bashir *et al.*, 2011). Furthermore, increasing the application of phosphorus from 0 to 60 kg ha⁻¹ gives the higher result of plant height and dry weight, nodules, a number of pods and grain yield of legumes (Mebrahtu and Teklay, 2021; Jaisankar and Manivannan, 2018; Carsky *et al.*, 2001), indeed the soil of Dore Baffano have Andic property (Nigussie *et al.*, 2021) which mostly inhibit the availability of P in the soil through precipitation and sorption processes (Sigaye *et al.*, 2020) and inhibits nitrogen fixation and crop production of legumes; this can be resolved through phosphorus and vermicompost application; moreover in addition to its substantial nutrient supply, vermicompost application helps to improve the availability of P by the mineralization of organic P. Thus, to introduce an economical and healthy source of nitrogen fertilizer for the soil in the study area convincing research works need to be done on vermicompost application and Rhizobium inoculation. Therefore, this study was initiated to evaluate the influence of Rhizobium inoculation, P fertilization, and vermicompost application on the Production of haricot bean as well as on the soil properties at Dore baffano woreda, kareso kebele in Sidama region.

1.2.General objective

The general objective of this study was to investigate the effect of rhizobium inoculation, P fertilization and vermicompost application on the selected soil Properties, Haricot bean productivity and biological N fixation.

1.2.1. Specific Objectives

- To evaluate the effect of rhizobium inoculation, Phosphorus and vermicompost application on estimate of BNF by haricot bean.
- To find out the effects of rhizobium inoculation, Phosphorus and vermicompost application on the growth and yield of haricot bean.
- To determine rhizobium inoculation, P and vermicompost application effect on selected physico-chemical properties of soil.
- To determine the most economically feasible fertilization for soil fertility and Haricot bean production at Dore Baffano.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Soil fertility depletion in Ethiopia

Ethiopia is considered as one of the most vulnerable countries in sub-Saharan Africa in soil fertility and nutrient reduction rates because of its mountainous geomorphology and ferocious husbandry systems grounded on small cereals (Van Beek *et al.*, 2016). Soil fertility depletion affects food security and leads to worsening rural poverty of African smallholder farmers by affecting the farming system (Bationo, 2009), especially in areas like East African soils including in Kenya, Tanzania and Ethiopia (Bekunda *et al.*, 2002; Raimi *et al.*, 2017).

Soil fertility depletion is the major factor that limits the productivity of crop for the small holder farmers in Ethiopia. Extensive farm cultivation, soil erosion and lack of awareness by the farmer on how to manage their farm land are some of the major causes for the degradation (Zelleke *et al.*, 2010). The degradation of soils affects the soil properties and nutrients because the properties change as external factors (erosion, chemical fertilizer etc.) act on the soil (Bezuayehu *et al.*, 2002). Thus, degradation of soil fertility must be considered an important consequence of agriculture unless careful attention is paid to nutrient conservation and replenishment, through inorganic and organic fertilization, recycling of agricultural wastes and biological N-fixation.

2.2. Haricot bean production in Ethiopia

Haricot bean is an important legume crop distributed and grown in different parts of Ethiopia depending on climatic and socio-economic factors. In recent years, production of grain legumes in Ethiopia has been increasing at a growth rate of 3.78% per annum (Erana, 2019). Leguminous crops are the third-largest export crop in Ethiopia' following coffee and sesame and highly contribute to the national economy (IFPRI, 2010). Oromia, Amhara, Southern Nations, Nationalities and Peoples region (SNNPR) are the major legume producing areas among all regions of the country with highest percentage of cultivated area coverage 42.40%, 39.91%, 14.75% of land respectively (Getachew, 2019).

In 2020-2021 cropping seasons Ethiopia obtains (552,564.07t) total haricot bean yield production with total area coverage of (3.065 million ha) (CSA, 2021). According to CSA (2018), the average national haricot bean production during 2016-17 cropping season was about 1.7 t ha⁻¹, however in research fields about 3.4 t ha⁻¹ of haricot bean production can be obtained.

The occurrence of disease, limited distribution of improved haricot bean varieties, minimum irrigation level and low soil fertility management is among the several factors for the low production rate of haricot bean in farmers' fields (Bekele et al., 2019 :ITC, 2019). However, many reports showed that the main cause of low productivity is due to low fertilizer application rate, since the crop requires optimum fertilizer application in order to give its best potential yield, but the low availability of fertilizer and the purchasing capacity of the farmers can be pointed as one of the major constraint for the low productivity of haricot bean on the farmers land (IFPRI, 2010; Lemu, 2016).

According to Gereziher et al. (2017), haricot bean is produced almost in all parts of the country with varying yield intensity, such as Oromia (mainly East Shewa, East Hararghe, and West Hararghe, West Arsi, and Arsi zones), SNNPR (Wolaita, Gedeo, Hlaba, Dauro and Guraghe zones) and Sidama region are the potential haricot bean production areas (Kassa, 2014). Generally, Lemu (2016) reported that good production of haricot bean is obtained in the Rift Valley areas of the country, due to the growing nature of the crop which favors low to mid altitude. Moreover, Oromia, Amhara, Southern Nations, Nationalities and Peoples region (SNNPR) are the major production areas with production rate of 51%, 24 % and 21% respectively (Worku, 2015). It is a highly preferable grain legume by most Ethiopian farmers due to its fast maturity and high protein content in its nutritional value and helps to keep other demand of the households through income generation by selling in local market as well as international markets. Haricot bean in Ethiopia is grown predominantly by smallholder producers and is one of the fast expanding legume crops that provide an essential part of the daily diet and foreign earnings for most Ethiopians (Girma, 2009; Abebe, 2020).

Haricot bean is one of the main potential and cash crop at hawassa zuria (Worku, 2015). However the production potential has many hindering factors, such as seed quality, loss of soil fertility, different socio economic factors, inadequate land preparation, using

inappropriate planting density, poor weed control, inadequate use of fertilizers are some of the factors. Lower usage of fertilizer like phosphorus in per hectare of land decreases haricot bean production by 31% (Abele and Tefera, 2015). Due to their crucial role in growth and development, plants need nitrogen and phosphorus are more than any other mineral nutrient (Brown et al., 2022). However, most farmer fields are these elements are deficient as a result of losses via leaching, volatilization, fixing and so on (Nigussie *et al.*, 2021). The main causes of the low yield and inability of the crop to reach its maximum productivity were continuous cultivation, biomass harvesting without replenishment and minimal or no fertilizer application.

In order to alleviate haricot bean yield decreasing impact due to fertilizer, several fertilizer experimental trials like Sigaye *et al.*, (2020) Ahmee and Sigaye, (2020) who work on the response of haricot bean due to phosphorus fertilization and blended fertilizer and bio-fertilizer effect respectively are done at Hawassa zuria. However the potential of haricot bean production of the area is not sufficient due to lack of fertilizer use awareness and less purchasing ability of the farmer, hence substantial fertilizer like vermicompost use along with phosphorus and rhizobium could be yield improving mechanism (Tadese, 2017; Birhanu, 2020).

2.3. Biological nitrogen fixation (BNF)

BNF is a biological atmospheric N₂-fixing Process, that involves symbiotic relations of legumes and microbial inoculants containing the living cells of effective strains (Gidago *et al.*, 2011). These microbial inoculants are biological fertilizers that include plant growth-promoting bacteria's such as Rhizobium, Cyanobacteria, Azotobacter and Azospirillum (Basalingappa, 2018). Among these, rhizobium bacteria's are symbiotic soil organisms, which enable legumes to use or 'fix' atmospheric nitrogen for plant growth in which each species of legume has a specific strain of rhizobium that is needed for the process (Berger *et al.*, 2013).

Some Rhizobium–legume associations will form nodules with a range of rhizobia which involves the recognition of the bacterium by the host and of the host by the bacterium through the exchange of signal compounds, while other legumes are very specific and the legume only form nodules when infected with a specific rhizobium (Yaseen et al., 2013; Hasan, 2018). As (Basalingappa, 2018) reported, soils also contain free living N₂ fixing bacteria like Azotobacter.

This bacterium belongs to non –symbiotic nitrogen fixing genera which are distributed in soils with limited number and activity, and has the ability to produce substances, such as vitamin B complex and growth-promoting hormones which have great potential in increasing plant growth and development to obtain high crop yield.

2.3.1. Importance of biological nitrogen fixation

The process of N₂ fixation feeds the legume crop with N and release high-quality organic matter to the soil which help to increase soil nutrient and water retention (Stagnari *et al.*,2017). Biological nitrogen fixation on the earth surface is estimated to be 150 to 200 million tons annually (Dash and Deole, 2019). Biological nitrogen fixation by legumes helps for the recycling of N in cropping systems and contributes for the improvement of mineral N availability in the soil (Signorelli *et al.*, 2020).

Under optimum growing conditions, fixed nitrogen by bacteria becomes available to other organisms in which more N₂ is fixed and converted to ammonia rapidly than the cell can assimilate to form new protein and the excess one excreted as NH₄ or amino acids (Bado et al .,2018). Bacteria may carry on fixation at a rate in excess of the requirements of the host, and this excess diffuses from the nodules or roots into the soil. After N₂-fixing bacteria die, their protein (containing the fixed nitrogen), is subject to ammonification by proteolytic microorganisms in the soil (Prevost And Bromfield, 2003). An experiment by Deaker *et al.*, (2004) shows that inoculation of legume crops increased nodulation and N₂ fixation which results in better crop production.

For most legumes, 50 to 80% of their total nitrogen requirements is obtained from biological fixation which reduces the use of synthetic fertilize and ameliorates soil fertility enrichment capacity (Dash and Deole, 2019).In recent years, the use of BNF has shown satisfying results for plenty of agricultural work of smallholder farmers (O’Hara, 1998). This Multipurpose and reliable technology is preferred by most farmers due to its high N source from symbiotic N₂-fixation by legumes.

The fixed N by legume is primarily utilized by the legume and excess N will be released to the soil and as when the biomass of the legume plant after harvest becomes degraded, the nutrient N will be added to the soil. The addition of nitrogen to the soil helps for the growth and yield

increment of neighboring crops which may be planted with the legume as intercropping or in seasonal rotational crops. Generally, BNF helps to fertilize the soil for future harvest crops other than N₂ fixing legume and reduces the utilization of synthetic fertilizers (Soumare *et al.*, 2020) .

One of the hindering factors for yield reduction of crops in most farmers' fields is due to the minimum application of fertilizers (Liu *et al.*, 2020). The increasing cost of fertilizer is the major constraint of low crop production especially for farmers in developing countries like Ethiopia (Rashid Shahidur and Minot Nicholas, 2014). In recent years, fertilizer costs have increased by nearly 50% (N fertilizer and DAP costs increased by 60% and 54% respectively) (Schnitkey *et al.*, 2021), hence biological nitrogen fixation is one of the most recognized alternative methods of providing nitrogen to the soil to improve crop production (Sanginga, 2003).

Most crops are only able to take up 30%- 50% of the fertilizer that is applied depending on the crop variety and type (Tabak *et al.*, 2020). Fertilizers that may not be taken up by plants (due to excessive use or leaching problems) can accumulate in soil, water, and the atmosphere and contribute to the greenhouse effect and stratospheric ozone depletion (Hakeem *et al.*, 2016; Berg *et al.*, 2017). About 300 Tg of CO₂ per year was released into the atmosphere from agricultural global fertilizer applications (Hakeem *et al.*, 2016). This CO₂ which is one of the GHG is released during the synthesis process of N-fertilizer derives from fossil energy, and contributes for global climate change. GHG which is also mainly resulting from the application of nitrogen fertilizers is N₂O, which is much more powerful in causing global warming than CO₂ and contributes 5-6 % Of total atmospheric GHG (Stagnari *et al.*, 2017).

Symbiotic biological N₂ fixation reduces the need of synthetic fertilizer and helps to have to healthy environment by avoiding pollution of water bodies, water flora and fauna due to eutrophication (caused due to leached nutrients from agricultural soil), and acidification of soil through continuous N fertilizer application.

2.3.2. Factors affecting biological nitrogen fixation

Identifying the constraints that limit N₂ fixation is important for both soil fertility and agronomic practice in which effective N₂ fixation by legumes is dependent on the efficiency and survival of rhizobium in soil (Slattery *et al.*, 2004). There are several factors affecting BNF in soil including acidity through Aluminum (Al) and Manganese (Mn), salinity, alkalinity (high concentrations of calcium (Ca) and boron (B), soil temperature, moisture, fertility - nutrient deficiencies and soil

structure affect all stages of the symbiosis and limit rhizobia growth and survival in soils (Kellman, 2008b).

The survival and multiplication of rhizobia in the soil is influenced by extremely high and low temperatures which lead to the suppression of bacterial growth and N fixation reduction in the root zone. Besides, the moisture status of soil is one of the major factors that affect BNF and has a major impact on nodulation and N fixation in legumes (Hungria and Vargas, 2000). High or minimum soil water can greatly affect the rate of N₂ fixation because of inadequate aeration in saturated soil and reduced water availability in dry soils at critical times during development and growth.

Besides, rhizobia competes with other soil organisms, including other bacteria, fungi and protozoa in soils (Hungria and Vargas, 2000; Belete *et al.*, 2019). Naturally existing rhizobia populations in soils may not be as effective as inoculant strains in N₂ fixation; somehow they can compete well with introduced strains for nodule formation (Sajid *et al.*, 2011). However, strains of rhizobia differ widely in their ability to survive, nodulate and fix N in the soil environment. Thus, in order to minimize this problem strain selection plays an important role (Tena *et al.*, 2016; Gebrehana and Dagnaw, 2020). High nutrient inputs in agricultural soils are the other major factor that affects rhizobia growth, nodulation, N₂ fixation and yield in legumes (Bhattacharjee and Dey, 2014). According to the suggestion of different authors, the most inhibiting nutrient for N₂ fixation is Nitrogen (Basalingappa, 2018; Buraka, 2019). The availability of high inorganic N in the rhizosphere inhibits N fixation by limiting the symbiosis of rhizobium-legume and reducing N fixation (Mulambula *et al.*, 2019).

2.3.3. Phosphorus fertilization effect on Biological N₂- fixation

The root nodulation and N fixation of legumes is significantly affected by the availability of P (Mills *et al.*, 2004). Phosphorus plays an important role in the symbiotic process of N₂ fixation by increasing root growth which helps to increase the ability of that plant to fix N, reducing the time for nodules development to become active early and for the benefit of the host legume and for improving the density of rhizobia bacteria in the soil surrounding the root (Fituma *et al.*, 2018; Gebremariam, 2021).

P is an essential nutrient for Rhizobium bacteria to convert atmospheric N₂ into ammonium NH₄ (useable by plants) (Musyoka, 2014). Rhizobium bacteria are able to synthesize the enzyme

nitrogenase which catalyzes the conversion of N_2 to two molecules of ammonia (NH_3). The pink color which can be observed in nodules indicates effective N_2 fixation, due to the presence of a protein called leghemoglobin. This protein contains oxygen-binding nutrients (Fe and Mo) and creates a nodule environment with lower oxygen which allows rhizobium bacteria to live and fix N_2 (Miriko, 2018). Phosphorus is involved as an energy source when 16 molecules of adenosine triphosphate (ATP) are converted to adenosine diphosphate (ADP) as each molecule of N_2 is reduced to NH_3 (Gabisa *et al.*, 2017). P-deficient haricot bean shows poor nodulation and plant growth especially; during the critical growth periods of the crop (seedling and root development), a readily available supply of P is needed from the soil (Gidago *et al.*, 2011; Zebire and Gelgelo, 2019).

2.3.4. Estimation methods of Biological Nitrogen Fixation

To determine the amount of nitrogen fixed, accurate measurement of symbiotic biological N fixation by legumes is important. Various methods are developed for the estimation of legume BNF under field conditions (Bado *et al.*, 2018), which include the DM yield method, the total N-balance method, the N-difference method, the ureide method, the acetylene reduction assay (ARA) and the ^{15}N isotope method (Unkovich And Pate, 2000; Herridge *et al.*, 2008). However, application of these methods depends on the environmental conditions, the purpose of the experiment and the available resources.

Total N accumulated is the simplest estimate of the amount of N fixed. However, it over estimates N fixation because it assumes that the crop derives its entire nutrient N from BNF (Herridge *et al.*, 2008). In N deficient soils, which are plant growth limiting, the dry matter yield of the legume plant is positively correlated with the amount of N from fixation. This method is simple, cheap and non-destructive, but it used to record only fresh weight. The other cheap, reliable and easily applicable method of BNF estimation is the N difference method (ACIAR, 2008). This method is simple, affordable, and easier for implementation without the need of qualified expertise and measures based on estimating how much N is accumulated by N_2 -fixing plants compared to non-fixing reference crop under optimum soil N levels. However, to have accurate estimation, the legume and reference crops must absorb similar amounts of nitrogen from the soil. Otherwise, incorrect estimation of N_2 fixation may result (Danso, 1993; Yu *et al.*, 2010).

However, to overcome the limiting factors of the above methods, ^{15}N isotope method provides more direct and precise measure of N fixation (Azam and Farooq, 2003) despite its expensive cost and difficulty to implement without expertise. It can provide an integrated measurement of the amount of fixed N accumulated by a crop over the growing season and the method can be applied directly in the field and can classify fixed N from soil-derived N (Herridge et al., 2008; Unkovich *et al.*, 2010).

2.4. Vermicompost

Vermicompost is a nutrient-rich organic material obtained by earthworms ingested biomass after undergoing physical, chemical, and microbial transformation (Olle, 2019). This transformation is done through the technology called vermicomposting, which is used to recycle available organic matter under mesophilic conditions, earthworms are the crucial drivers of the process and act as mechanical blenders, and by fragmenting the organic matter they modify its physical and chemical status by gradually reducing the C:N and increasing the surface area exposed to microorganisms - thus making it much more favorable for microbial activity and further decomposition (Chanu *et al.*, 2018).

2.4.1. Properties of Vermicompost

The final output of vermicompost is usually odorless and Dark brown to black in color with low bulk density ($0.7\text{--}0.96\text{ g/cm}^3$) and optimum moisture content (Kabi, 2016). Several studies pointed to vermicompost as the nutrient-rich source of nitrogen, potassium, phosphorus, calcium, magnesium along with the other micronutrient (Satpathy *et al.*, 2020; (Sinha *et al.*, 2009). The C:N of vermicast ranges from 10.31-17.51 which is used to indicate the maturation of vermicompost, along with this organic Carbon in vermicast ranges 14.3-37%, total N 1.3-4%, phosphorus 1.55–2.25% and potassium 1.85–2.25%. Vermicompost also contains the secondary essential elements Ca, Mg and S (Xu and Mou, 2016; Kumar and Kumar, 2017) along with micronutrients Fe, B, Mn, Zn and Cu. the nutrient level of vermicompost varies depending on the type of feeding material that is digested by the vermiworms (Azarmi et al., 2008; Ramnarain et al., 2019). Vermicompost has been scientifically proven to have high amount of beneficial soil microbes like ‘nitrogen-fixing bacteria’ and mycorrhizal fungi and also used as a soil conditioner and plant growth enhancer (Deaker et al., 2004).

2.4.2. Effect of Vermicompost on the property of soils

Different authors confirmed that continuous application of vermicompost resulted in improvement of soil structure, aeration, infiltration, and drainage (Manivannan *et al.*, 2009). A study by Azarmi *et al.* (2008), showed that the application of vermicompost on soil influences the degree of soil aggregation, reduce bulk density and increases total porosity, moisture-holding capacity, cation-exchange capacity, and oxidation potential of soil caused by increased microbial activity. application of vermicompost on soil shows a significant increase on the level of N, P, K and enhances crop growth and productivity (Sinha *et al.*, 2009).

Azarmi *et al.* (2008) evaluated the effects of vermicompost on soil chemical properties, showing that application of vermicompost enhanced total organic carbon, total N, P, K, Ca, Zn, Mn. Humic substance present in vermicompost helps the soil by transferring humified components to the soil, as well as increasing plant growth, humic acid increases root hair proliferation, and mineral nutrient release, and also involved in cell respiration, photosynthesis, oxidative phosphorylation, protein synthesis, and various enzymatic reactions (Argaw and Mnalku, 2017).

The population of N₂-fixing bacteria and actinomycetes increases through the application of vermicompost (Lemma and Abera, 2020). Thus microbial activities improve the availability of soil P and nitrogen (Ansari and Ismail 2012) and it plays vital role on the general property of soil unlike inorganic fertilizers which used to fulfill only the crop need for the growing period.

2.4.3. Effect Vermicompost on haricot bean production

Vermicompost stimulates microbial activity in soils, improves nutrient content and increases the growth, yield and quality of crops (Sinha *et al.*, 2009). The growth and yield of legume crops are significantly influenced by the application of vermicompost (Ebrahim *et al.*, 2012) due to the high levels of organic matter content in the soil that ensure higher microbial activity and greater soil nitrogen-providing ability than soil managed through inorganic source (Mathenge *et al.*, 2018).

Earthworm burrows lined with earthworm casts act as an excellent medium for harboring nitrogen-fixing bacteria, particularly of gram-negative bacteria, which increased significantly after the application of vermicompost in soil (Lazcano and domínguez, 2011). Therefore, this

organic compost creates a suitable growth medium for haricot bean growth (Kellman, 2008). The study of Argaw and Mnalku, (2017) on the application effect of vermicompost on rhizobium inoculation, nodulation and yield shows a significant effect, which is mostly due to the increasing population of useful soil microbes for the soil through the application of vermicompost, such as *Azotobacter chroococcum*, *Azotobacter vinelandii*, *Bacillus stearothermophilus*, *Bacillus megaterium*, *Pseudomonas putida*, and *Bacillus subtilis* are important to facilitate atmospheric nitrogen fixation by legumes and to maximize grain yield (Asrin *et al.*, 2019).

2.5. Phosphorus fertilization Effect on the production of haricot bean

The high-quality production of legumes mainly depends on the amount of P taken up by the grain (Khan *et al.*, 2003; Sigaye *et al.*, 2020), which makes it the most essential element for the proper production of grain legumes (Brady and Weil, 2002). Legume crops including Faba bean haricot bean, chick pea and others have high P requirements because they use it for the production of protein-containing compounds. Lack of optimum P application is one of the several yield-reducing factors contributing to the low Haricot bean yield in Ethiopia (Gidago *et al.*, 2011b). An adequate supply of P early in the life of a plant is important in the development of its reproductive parts.

The production of haricot bean in Ethiopia is far below its production capacity and this might be because 70% of Ethiopian soil is P deficient (Gabisa *et al.*, 2017), and more than 16.6 kg P ha⁻¹ is depleted from the agricultural soils of Ethiopia (Tamene *et al.*, 2017). P sufficiency for crop growth does not always exist in most soils due to low available phosphorus (Brady and Weil, 2002). Somehow, in order to decrease the yield reduction caused by P deficiency, many research works have been conducted. According to the findings of experimental research, the application of P increases the yield and production of haricot beans depending on the variety of the crop and soil type (Argaw and Akuma, 2015). The study of Kassa, (2014) evaluated haricot bean varieties response to the application of different P fertilizer rate on acid soils and found that the application of P show significant change on the yield and yield components of the crop. Similarly, the finding of Sigaye *et al.*, (2020) shows that P application in soil results better haricot bean yield increment.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. Description of the study area

The field experiment was conducted at Dore Baffano wereda, Kareso kebele, which is located in Sidama region, and is about 15 km from Hawassa town and 287 km south of Addis Ababa. The study area is found 7⁰ 06 N and 38⁰ 23 E latitudes at an altitude of 1743 m.a.s.l. The mean annual rainfall is 957 mm with the main rainy season extending from April to September. The mean annual temperature is 20.5 °C with mean maximum and minimum temperature of 27 and 13 °C respectively. The most dominant crops cultivated in the study area are maize, and common bean. the major soil type of the area is Andic Cambisols (Nigussie *et al.*, 2021).

Figure 1: Map showing location of the study site

Figure 2: Annual rainfall and average monthly maximum and minimum temperature of Hawassa Zuria (2002-2021) average) (HNMSA, 2021).

3.2. Experimental design and Treatments

The experiment was conducted using factorial Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD), with three replications. The experiment have 3 factors and will be done in a factorial combinations of two levels of Rhizobium inoculation (inoculated and non-inoculated) 3 levels of phosphorus (0, 30, and 60 kg ha^{-1}) and 3level of VC (0, 2.5 and 5 t ha^{-1}) and there will be 18 treatment combination. Haricot bean, variety Hawassa Dume is used as test crop.

Table 1: Treatment combination

Treatment	Rhizobium	Phosphorus (kg ha^{-1})	VC rate(t ha^{-1})	Treatment combination
1	Non-inoculated	0	0	Control
2	Non-inoculated	30	0	-RH+ 30P+ 0VC
3	Non-inoculated	60	0	-RH+ 60P+ 0VC
4	Non-inoculated	0	2.5	-RH+ 0P+ 2.5VC
5	Non-inoculated	30	2.5	-RH+ 30P+ 2.5VC
6	Non-inoculated	60	2.5	-RH+ 60P+ 2.5VC
7	Non-inoculated	0	5	-RH+ 0P+ 5VC
8	Non-inoculated	30	5	-RH+ 30P+ 5VC
9	Non-inoculated	60	5	-RH+ 60P+ 5VC
10	Inoculated	0	0	+RH+ 0P+ 0VC
11	Inoculated	30	0	+RH+ 30P+ 0VC
12	Inoculated	60	0	+RH+ 60P+ 0VC
13	Inoculated	0	2.5	+RH+ 0P+ 2.5VC
14	Inoculated	30	2.5	+RH+ 30P+ 2.5VC
15	Inoculated	60	2.5	+RH+ 60P+2.5VC
16	Inoculated	0	5	+RH+ 0P+ 5VC
17	Inoculated	30	5	+RH+ 30P+ 5VC
18	Inoculated	60	5	+RH+ 60P+ 5VC

3.3. Planting material

The Haricot bean variety (Hawassa Dume) was used as planting material selected based on numerous advantages including wide area adaptation, its largest biomass and grain yield potential, with high market demand and wide consumption by local farmers. Hawassa Dume has medium-sized dark red grain color and white flower color with a maturity period of 85-90 days with a determinate growth habit. The variety is adapted to an altitude range of 1100-1750 meters above sea level with rainfall of more than 500 mm in the growing season. Rhizobium strain (HB-429) was obtained from Menagesha Biotechnology PLC, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, which was used as an inoculant for the haricot bean seed. This strain has been proven to enhance the nodulation capacity, agronomic, and yield performance of haricot bean variety (Hawassa Dume) and was used as planting material selected based on numerous.

3.4. Experimental procedure

The experimental Plot was 4m x 4m = 16m² with 0.5m spacing between plots. Haricot bean seeds planted 40 cm and 10cm spaced between row and plant respectively. At sowing, haricot bean seeds were coated with rhizobia cells per gram of the inoculant which is 10g/kg seeds, using sugar solution (10%) as the adhesive agent for the seed (Worku, 2015). The sugar slurry was gently mixed with dry seed and then with carrier-based inoculants so that all the seeds received a thin coating of the inoculants. In order to avoid cross-contamination, non-inoculated seed was sown first. Vermicompost application was done on a dry-weight basis and was mixed well with the soil after application. TSP fertilizer was applied at the side of the sowing point at planting. As a non-fixing reference crop local wheat variety was used for estimation of biological nitrogen fixation (Unkovich *et al.*, 2008). It was sown as a drill with 30 cm within a row on 4.8m² plot areas and all management and treatments are applied as that of haricot bean.

3.5. Vermicompost preparation

The vermicompost was prepared from locally available wastes such as chopped enset leaf and steam, coffee husk, banana pill and animal manures and it was prepared by local farmers

following the appropriate procedure. After the preparation of the fine and final product of vermicompost sample was taken for laboratory analysis.

3.6. Soil sample preparation

Representative composite soil sample (30 sub samples per composite) was collected before planting at rooting depth (0-30cm) following the standard soil sampling procedure using auger. Each composite soil sample was subjected for soil physicochemical analysis. Post-harvest soil sample was collected for each plot of the experiment from 5 points at rooting depth (30cm) using auger. The collected samples were subjected to dry in air and sieved to pass in to 2 mm sieve. Soil moisture status was measured 4 times including the initial at 30, 60, and 90 days after planting during the cropping season of haricot bean using core sampler from each plot. Soil sample is collected in a moisture can and wet weight of the sample is recorded. The soil sample is dried in hot air oven at 105 °C until constant weight is obtained for 24 constant hours and dry weight of the sample is recorded following this process moisture content is calculated using the following formula (Anon, 1990)

Moisture content (on dry weight basis) = $\frac{\text{Wet weight}-\text{Dry weight}}{\text{Dry weight}} \times 100$

Dry weight

3.7. Laboratory analysis

3.7.1. Physico-chemical analysis of soil and vermicompost

Collected soil and vermicompost samples were subjected to physical and chemical analysis. Soil texture was determined using Bouyoucos hydrometer (Bouyoucos, 1962). Bulk density was estimated from undisturbed soil samples collected using core sampler following the method used by Blake and Hartge, (1986). The pH of soil was determined using 1:2.5 of water suspension method by using pH meter and pH of vermicompost was determined using 1:5 watersuspension. The organic carbon content of the soil andvermicompostwas analysedfollowing the wet digestion method,which involvesdigestion of the organic carbon in the soilsamples with potassium dichromate ($K_2Cr_2O_7$) in sulfuric acid solution(Walkley and Black, 1934). Total nitrogen was analyzed using the Kjeldahl method (Sahlemeden and Taye, 2000). The Kjeldahl procedure is based on the principle that the organic matter is oxidized by treating soil

with concentrated sulfuric acid, nitrogen in the organic nitrogenous compounds being converted into ammonium sulfate during the oxidation. Available phosphorus was determined by Olsen method (Olsen *et al.*, 1954). The absorbance of available phosphorus extracted by method was measured using spectrophotometer after color development. Available sulfur will be determined by KH_2PO_4 extract (Manohar, 2013). The exchangeable bases (Ca, Mg, K and Na) and Cation exchange capacity was measured after saturating the soil with 1N ammonium acetate (NH_4OAC) and displacing it with 1 N NaOAC (Reeuwijk, 2002). Exchangeable Ca and Mg will be measured from the extract with atomic absorption spectrophotometer while exchangeable K and Na was determined from the same extracts with flame photometer (Gustav, 1961). Available micronutrients (Fe, Mn, Zn and Cu) was extracted by diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (DTPA) method (Lindsay and Norvell, 1978) and measured using atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

3.8. Estimate of biological nitrogen fixation

Haricot bean plant samples were collected from 1m x 1.5m quadrat of each plot at physiological maturity. The reference crop (wheat) was harvested, labeled, and dried in a paper bag in the oven at 70°C for 48 hours and dry matter was measured for each sample using a sensitive balance. The samples were crushed and sieved to pass in to 1 mm sieve and prepared for determination of N uptake. The total nitrogen was analyzed by using the Kjeldahl method (Sahlemeden and Taye, 2000) using (Burettes, Pipettes, Erlenmeyer flasks - 250 ml, Magnetic stirrer, and Kjeldahl flasks 300ml) apparatus. The Kjeldahl procedure is based on the principle that by treating plant material with concentrated oxidized sulfuric acid and nitrogen in the plant material is converted into ammonium sulfate during the oxidation. The ammonia liberated in the distillation process with NaOH is trapped by the acid. The ammonia is adsorbed in the form of NH_4^+ ion in boric acid and back titrated with standard H_2SO_4 . The N yield was calculated as the product of the nutrient N concentration and dry matter yield of haricot bean as described by (Unkovich *et al.*, 2008). After N analysis the BNF was estimated using the N difference method. The N difference method is the simplest method used to calculate the difference of N accumulated in N_2 -fixing and non-fixing plants. The main assumption is that the N_2 -fixing plants take up the same amount of soil mineral N as the non- N_2 -fixing plants given that the plants' rooting depth is comparable. There the following equation was used.

N Fixed = N –yield fixing plant – N-yield reference plant (Unkovich *et al.*, 2008).

%Ndfa = 100(TNf – TN ref) / TNf (Bliss and and Hardson, 1993)

Where: %Ndfa is the nitrogen derived from the atmosphere and N-yield is the total nitrogen accumulated in both the fixing and non-fixing plants.

TNf is the total N-content of fixing plants and **TN ref** is the total N-content of reference crop.

3.9. Data collection

3.9.1. Phonological parameters

Days to 50 % flowering: It was recorded as the number of days required from planting to the time when 50% of plants in the plot shows flower.

Days to 90% physiological maturity: It was recorded as the number of days required from planting to the time when 90% of plants showed a gray color in each pot before senescence.

3.9.2. Growth parameters

Leaf number: It was counted from 5 randomly selected plants from each plot at physiological maturity.

Plant height (cm): It was measured from 5 randomly selected plants using meter.

Number of branches per plant: It was counted from 5 randomly selected plants from each plot at physiological maturity.

Leaf area index (LAI): was measured from 5 random plants and calculated using the following formula:-

LAI= leaf area m² / ground area m²

3.9.3. Yield and yield components

Number of pods and Number of seeds per pod was counted from 5 randomly selected plants.

Grain Yield (kg) Haricot Bean yield was measured from each plot (from 5m²) using standard sensitive balance and grain moisture content was measured using grain moisture tester ;grain yield was adjusted by 10% this is because it is the suitable temperature level in order to maintain its viability for a long time (Worku, 2015).

Hundred Seed weight (gm) was measured by taking a random harvested grain yield from each haricot bean plot using sensitive balance.

Above ground dry biomass was measured using balance for each plot after drying the above ground biomass of the haricot bean for 48 hr. at 70⁰c.

Harvest index (%) was calculated by dividing grain yield ha⁻¹ by dray biomass ha⁻¹ as follows: -

$$\text{Harvest index (\%)} = \frac{\text{grain yield} \times 100}{\text{Above ground dry biomass}}$$

3.10. Economic analysis

3.10.1. Total variable cost

Total variable cost of Vermicompost, Rhizobium, fertilizer cost and experimental field operations was some of the variable costs considered in the experiments.

3.10.2. Gross and net benefit

Gross field benefit of each treatment was computed by multiplying price of Kg of Haricot bean yield in the study area for one-hectare field. Net benefit was calculated by subtracting the total variable costs that vary from the gross field benefit for each treatment. The process of calculating the Marginal rate of return of alternative treatments, proceeding in steps from the least costly treatment to the most costly, and deciding if they are acceptable to farmers, is called marginal analysis (CIMMYT, 1988), which will be adjusted by following formula.

$$\text{MRR} = \frac{\text{Change of net benefit} \times 100}{\text{Change of cost}} \dots\dots\dots (\text{CIMMYT, 1988})$$

3.11. Data analysis

Analysis of variance was conducted for each of the measured (computed) parameters. All yield components and soil data was subjected to analysis of variance using SAS version 9.4 (SAS, 2013). List Significant difference (LSD) at 5% probability level was used for mean separation when analysis of variance indicated the presence of significant differences (Gomez and Gomez, 1984).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Selected physico-chemical properties of soil and vermicompost characterization

4.1.1. Selected soil physico-chemical properties

The results of the initial soil analysis revealed that the soil particles distributed in the sites were composed of various materials such as sand, silt, and clay. Based on the FOA classification, the sites' textural class was indicated to be sandy loam. The soil pH was slightly acidic at 6.7. According to Hzelton and Murphy, (2007), the soil bulk density of the experimental site of 1.2 g/cm³ was rated as low, and it's found to be the ideal bulk density for plant growth. It also has a higher pore space of 55.14%. The moisture of soil at field capacity before the experiment was recorded as 15.8%, which is below the optimum. According to (Sinha *et al.*,2009), the optimum soil moisture ranges from 20% to 60%. The total nitrogen of the site was recorded to be 0.11%, which is rated as low (Tekalign, 1991), which is insufficient for the growth of plant. The organic carbon of the site was recorded at 1.19 % which is low (Hzelton and Murphy, 2007). The available phosphorus in the initial soil was recorded to be 4.76 mg/kg, which is rated as low in the soil. The C:N in the initial soil was recorded as 11.36. Exchangeable calcium, magnesium, sodium, and potassium in the soil were (5.302, 0.42667, 0.21791, and 1.07808) cmol (+) kg⁻¹ respectively. The CEC of the experimental site soil was low, which is recorded to be 11.5 cmol (+) kg⁻¹. Micronutrients (iron, manganese, zinc, copper, and boron) in the initial soil were found to be 39.23, 9.44, 6.8, 0.79, and 0.001 mg/kg, respectively.

Table 2: physical and chemical properties of soil before planting

Parameters	Value	Rating for soil	Reference
Sand (%)	53		
Clay (%)	11		
Silt (%)	36		
Textural Class	sandy loam		(Soil Survey Division Staff, 1993)
BD(g/cm ³)	1.2	Low	(Bache <i>et al.</i> , 2008)
MC (%)	15.8		
Porosity (%)	55.14		

pH H₂O (1:2.5)	6.7	Slightly acidic	(Tekalign, 1991)
EC(dsm⁻¹)	0.04	Non-saline	
TN (%)	0.11	Low	(Tekalign, 1991)
OC (%)	1.19	Low	(Tekalign, 1991)
P (mg/kg)	4.76	Very low	(Olsen, 1954)
C:N	11.36		
Ca(cmol (+) kg⁻¹)	5.302	Low	(FAO, 2006)
Mg(cmol (+) kg⁻¹)	0.42667	Low	(FAO, 2006)
Na (cmol (+) kg⁻¹)	0.21791	Low	(FAO, 2006)
K (cmol (+) kg⁻¹)	1.07808	High	(FAO, 2006)
CEC (cmol (+) kg⁻¹)	11.5	Moderate	(Hzelton and Murphy, 2007)
S mg/kg)	7.28	Very low	(Zbiral <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
Fe (mg/kg)	39.23	Very high	(Jones, J.Benton, 2002)
Mn (mg/kg)	9.44	Very high	(Jones, J.Benton, 2002)
Zn (mg/kg)	6.8	Very high	(Lindsay and Norvell, 1978)
Cu (mg/kg)	0.79	Medium	(Jones, J.Benton, 2002)
B (mg/kg)	< 0.001	Very low	(Jones, J.Benton, 2002)

4.1.2. Selected Physico-chemical Properties of Vermicompost

Vermicompost samples were analyzed for the physicochemical properties of soil including soil moisture, pH (H₂O), available phosphorus, total nitrogen, CEC (cation exchange capacity), exchangeable calcium, magnesium, sodium, and potassium, and micronutrients (iron, manganese, zinc, copper, and boron) (Table 3). The analysis result revealed that the pH and EC of vermicompost were 8.14 and 2.91 dS m⁻¹ respectively. According to Tekalign, (1991), this result was ranged as strongly alkaline; in agreement with this, Asrin *et al.*, (2019) and Lemma and Abera, (2020) reported the high pH value of vermicompost. According to Singh *et al.*, (2020), earthworms and microorganisms could tolerate soil pH 5.96–8.65 and an electrical conductivity of 8 dS m⁻¹ (Wako, 2021); therefore, the prepared vermicompost can be a suitable medium for earthworms and microorganisms. Total nitrogen and organic carbon in the vermicompost were found to be 0.93% and 12.5%, respectively. This result is supported by

Nagavallemma *et al.*, (2006) report, which investigated the higher value of nutrients in vermicompost, which is very helpful for the fertility of the soil and enhances the growth of crops when added to the soil. The nutrient content of vermicompost that is decomposed from different farmyard materials contains the highest nutrients (Ramnarain *et al.*,2019).

The available phosphorus in the vermicompost was found to be 642.8 mg/kg. This higher result of P might be obtained due to the mineralization and subsequent mobilization of phosphorous during vermicomposting by increased bacterial and phosphatase activities (Tesfaye, 2017); vermicompost contains more phosphorus up to two times more than ordinary compost ; in addition, during vermicomposting, worms change insoluble P into soluble forms with the help of P-solubilizing bacteria and phosphatases found in worm guts(Wako, 2021); in addition, higher phosphorus in vermicompost might be due to phosphorous mineralization during vermicomposting (Padmavathiamma *et al.*, 2008).

Table 3:-physico-chemical properties of vermicompost

Parameters	Value
MC (%)	39.2
pH H₂O (1:5)	8.5
EC(dsm-1)	2.91
TN (%)	0.93
OC (%)	12.45
P (mg/kg)	642.8
C:N	13.41
Ca(cmol (+) kg⁻¹)	28.92
Mg(cmol (+) kg⁻¹)	12.36
Na (cmol (+) kg⁻¹)	1.78
K (cmol (+) kg⁻¹)	25.65
CEC (cmol (+) kg⁻¹)	57.18
S mg/kg)	208.03
Fe (mg/kg)	17.04
Mn (mg/kg)	98.02
Zn (mg/kg)	36.24
Cu (mg/kg)	3.34
B (mg/kg)	3.72

The decomposed compost has a C: N ratio of 13.71, which favors net mineralization for nutrients such as NPK and therefore their availability in soil. The exchangeable calcium, magnesium,

sodium, and potassium of the soil were (28.92, 12.36, 1.78, and 25.65) cmol (+) kg⁻¹ respectively. The prepared vermicompost contains micronutrients such as iron (17.02), manganese (98.02 mg/kg), zinc (36.24 mg/kg), copper (3.34 mg/kg), and boron (3.72 mg/kg). Similarly, Geremu *et al.*, (2020) reported the highest value of micronutrients from vermicompost

4.2. Rhizobium inoculation, phosphorus rate and vermicompost application Effect on selected physicochemical properties of soil.

4.2.1. Rhizobium inoculation and vermicompost application Effect on Soil moisture content at different haricot bean growth stages

The percentage of soil moisture after 30 days of treatment application was very highly significantly ($p < .0001$) affected by vermicompost application, whereas the main effects (rhizobium inoculation and phosphorus rate) and the interaction effects are non-significant.

Table 4: Interaction effect Rhizobium inoculation with vermicompost on soil moisture content

VC rate(t ha ⁻¹)	60 day	
	Inoculated	Non-inoculated
0	20.69d	22.83c
2.5	25.41b	25.16b
5	27.21a	26.28ab
LSD (< 0.05)	0.5777	
RH*VC	0.0023	
CV (%)	5.09	

Mean values within a columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at $P \leq 0.05$; CV= Coefficient of variation; VC=vermicompost

The application rate of 5t ha⁻¹ VC resulted the highest (25.79%) percentage of soil moisture, while the lowest (20.99%) MC was obtained from the control treatment at 30 days. Application of vermicompost in to soil increases the water holding capacity of soil in agreement with this Tharmaraj *et al.*, (2011) found the highest moisture content of soil due to vermicompost application.

The percentage of soil moisture at 60 days was very highly significantly affected ($p < .0001$) by the main effect VC application and was highly significantly affected by the two-way interaction

effects (rhizobium inoculation with VC application), whereas the other main effects and interaction effects was non-significant in this parameter. Organic treatments like compost improve the moisture of soil due to their capacity to retain water.

The interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with VC rate shows a significant MC increment in the soil. The application effect of rhizobium inoculation with 5t ha⁻¹ VC results in the highest (27.21%) percentage of soil moisture, followed by 26.28%, which results from the interaction effect of non-rhizobium inoculation with 5t ha⁻¹ VC, while the lowest (20.69%) soil moisture content was obtained from the application of rhizobium inoculation with 0 t ha⁻¹ VC. These experiments showed that biological fertilizers improve the water-holding capacity of soil, keep moisture, and avoid dryness; likewise it reduces the application of additional water when it is applied under crop plantation, as well as helping the mobilization of nutrients through plant roots and enabling the roots to absorb nutrients more easily from the soil.

Soil moisture after 90 days of treatment application was highly significantly affected by the vermicompost application rate, while the other main effects and interaction effects are non-significant. The highest soil moisture (19.44%) at 90 days was recorded from the application rate of 5t ha⁻¹ VC, while the lowest soil moisture (15.13%) was recorded from the control treatment. This result was supported by the finding of Wakgari, (2021) on the increasing percentage of soil moisture due to application rate of vermicompost. This could be because vermicompost contains more colloidal components, such as earthworm mucus and polysaccharides, which function as water-absorbing agents and raise the soil's ability to store water. Additionally, the activity of the worms when they burrow has a significant impact on the permeability of water in the soil. Vermi-casts have the ability to store water eight to nine times their weight, further increasing the soil's fertility (Munnoli and Bhosle, 2011; Ibrahim *et al*, 2015). As it was measured under different growth stages of haricot bean (30, 60, and 90 days), application of 5t ha⁻¹ VC shows the highest percentage of soil moisture, and the interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation and the 5t ha⁻¹VC rate shows the vermicompost rate increases the soil moisture, and the interaction effect also significantly increases the percent of moisture.

Table 5: Effect of vermicompost on Soil moisture content

		30day	60 day	90 day
VC rate(t ha-1)	0	20.99 ^c	21.72 ^c	15.13 ^c
	2.5	23.08 ^b	25.21 ^b	16.79 ^b
	5	25.79 ^a	26.7 ^{5a}	19.44 ^a
LSD		0.7675	0.4128	0.5062
P value		<.0001	<.0001	0.0002
CV (%)		10.02	5.09	12.45

Mean values within a columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at $P \leq 0.05$; NS= non-significant; CV= Coefficient of variation; VC=vermicompost

4.2.2. Effects of rhizobium inoculation, phosphorus rate and VC rate on the selected chemical properties of soil.

Total soil nitrogen

Total soil nitrogen was significantly ($p=0.0205$) affected by Rhizobium inoculation and highly significantly affected by VC application, whereas phosphorus application and the other interaction effects shows non-significant effect.

Inoculation resulted the higher (0.12%) percentage of total soil nitrogen compared to the non-inoculated treatments which obtains 0.11% TN. In agreement with this result (Chimdi *et al.*, 2022), shows the effect of inoculation on increasing total nitrogen in the soil; similarly Khaitov *et al.*, (2016) and Omeke, (2017) found significantly higher value of soil total nitrogen due to rhizobium inoculation. This result might be obtained due to the attribution of nitrogen fixed by microorganism biologically, nitrogen-fixing bacteria use nitrogenase enzymes to convert tons of N atmospheric through fixation to ammonium (NH_4^+), nitrite (NO_2^-), and nitrates (NO_3^{2-}) and add it to the soil, allowing plants to survive in nutrient poor soils (Flores-Duarte *et al.*, 2022). In addition the increase in soil total nitrogen by rhizobium inoculation could have been caused due to action of rhizobium strains in improving soil nitrogen concentration. Rhizobium is a bio-fertilizer that increases soil nutrient content and enhances plant growth, during effective application in soil within the soil pH range. Rhizobium, existing in the root nodules of the leguminous plants, adds nitrogen to the soil by converting dinitrogen into ammonia (Verma *et al.*, 2022).

Application rate of 5t ha⁻¹ VC shows 15.35% higher value over the control, hence the highest 0.13% total N in the soil was obtained from 5t ha⁻¹ VC while the lowest 0.11% was obtained from control. This outcome might be obtained due to the addition of greater residual nitrogen that remains in the soil at the end of the growing season following the application of vermicompost to the soil and it is one of the major nutrient supplied to soil as organic matter added in the soil (Uz and Tavali, 2014), as well vermicompost is nutrient rich specially it contains higher amount of total nitrogen which is incorporated in the soil during VC application. In addition, the nitrogen released from compost during mineralization might be responsible for increasing value of total soil nitrogen due to VC application. The result of this experiment agreed with that of Bekele *et al.*, (2018) who reported increasing effect of vermicompost on soil nitrogen, this might be resulted because vermicompost stimulates microbial activities which transforms nitrogen into mucoprotein that reduces nutrient loss and decreases the risk of NO₃⁻ leaching from the soil (Masciandaro *et al.*, 2010), In agreement with this result increasing effect of vermicompost application accelerates the amount of total nitrogen in the soil (Azarmi *et al.*, 2008). Similarly, (Wagari *et al.*, 2022) also found the increasing effect of total soil nitrogen due to vermicompost application in an experiment done on sandy clay loam soil at western Ethiopia, Wollega zone.

Plant Available Phosphorus

Available soil phosphorus was very highly significantly ($p < 0.0001$) affected by the main effect (phosphorus rate and VC application) and by the two-way interaction effects (rhizobium inoculation with phosphorus rate and phosphorus rate with VC application), while the other interaction effect shows non-significant result on this parameter.

Available soil phosphorus significantly increases due to the interaction effect of rhizobium with phosphorus rate. The highest amount of available phosphorus (12.30 mg kg⁻¹) was obtained from the interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with 60kg ha⁻¹ P while the lowest (3.25 mg kg⁻¹) soil phosphorus was recorded from the control and showed 73.78% higher value over the control, followed by the interaction effect of 60kg ha⁻¹ P with non-rhizobium inoculation, which is 9.25mg kg⁻¹. According to (Olsen *et al.*, 1954), the result of both interaction effects was rated as high available phosphorus in the soil. This result agreed with the result of Chimdi *et al.*, (2022), who reported a significant result of soil P from the interaction effect of inoculation with P level at western Shewa. The increase in available soil phosphorus due to the interaction effect of

rhizobium inoculation with P application might be due to the release of P from the applied fertilizer and the ability of the rhizobium strain to convert non-available Phosphorus of the soil to available form (Mng'ong'o *et al.*,2023), in which Rhizobium is one of the common legume nodulating bacteria species that can solubilize Phosphorus from its insoluble sources and make it available by decreasing the soil pH through organic acids, which further mineralize organic P using acid and alkaline phosphatases, likewise Omeke, (2017) reported significantly higher value of available phosphorus rhizobium inoculation over the non-inoculated one.

Table 6: Interaction effect of rhizobium and phosphorus on soil available phosphorus

P rate(kg ha ⁻¹)	P (mg/kg)	
	Inoculated	Non-inoculated
0	4.48 ^d	3.71 ^d
30	5.68 ^c	6.28 ^c
60	12.39 ^a	9.21
LSD (< 0.05)	1.093	
RH*P	0.0001	
CV (%)	16.4	

Mean values within a columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at $P \leq 0.05$; CV= Coefficient of variation

The interaction effect of phosphorus rate with VC application significantly increases available soil phosphorus. According to the result of this experiment, the highest (14.12 mg kg⁻¹) available P was obtained from the interaction effect of 60kg ha⁻¹ P with 0t ha⁻¹ with 77.13% higher value than the control, whereas the lowest (3.23 mg kg⁻¹) was recorded from the control (Table 9). However, based on the results of this experiment, the overall result of this study agreed with the experimental finding of Alam *et al.*, (2013) which showed that phosphorus rate and VC application rate significantly increased the amount of available phosphorus in the soil. Application of phosphorus fertilizer increases available P in the soil Bekele *et al.*, (2018). Soil-available P shows a significant change due to VC application in P-deficient soil. A similar result was reported by Asrin *et al.*, (2019) on the significant effect of VC on soil-available phosphorus. This might be due to the activity of the phosphate enzyme, which is found in vermicompost, that increases phosphorus availability to plants (Kumar and Kumar, 2017; (Padmavathiamma *et al.*, 2008).

Organic Carbon

Organic Carbon was very highly significantly ($p=0.0001$) affected by main effect (rhizobium inoculation and VC application) and is significantly affected by the two-way interaction (rhizobium inoculation with VC application and phosphorus rate with VC application), while phosphorus rate and the other interaction effects are non-significant.

Table 7 Interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with vermicompost application on soil organic carbon

OC%		
VC rate(t ha ⁻¹)	Inoculated	Non-inoculated
0	1.37 ^c	1.17 ^d
2.5	1.44 ^b	1.32 ^c
2.5	1.68 ^a	1.36 ^c
LSD (< 0.05)	0.0737	
RH*VC	0.0019	
CV (%)	5.53	

Mean values within a columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at $P \leq 0.05$; CV= Coefficient of variation; VC=vermicompost

The interaction effect of inoculation with 5t ha⁻¹ VC rate results in the highest OC (1.68%) compared to the other treatments, whereas the lowest OC (1.17%) was recorded from the control. Similarly, Alkobaisy and Mutlag, (2021) reported that the interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with VC application significantly improves the organic matter of the soil. This might be due to the positive and highly significant correlation of soil total nitrogen with %OC ($r = 0.50^{***}$). (Appendix 2), this correlation between soil nitrogen and organic carbon was supported by Paul, (2022) report on the positive and strong correlation between soil nitrogen and organic carbon. A similarly experimental finding by Azarmi *et al.*, (2008) revealed an increasing level of soil organic carbon due to the increasing application of vermicompost on loamy soil. This might be due to the interaction effect of rhizobium with vermicompost, resulting growth regulators and enzymes that increase the amount of organic matter and elements, particularly macronutrients like N, P, and K, ready for the plant. In addition, VC application positively increases the percent of OC in the soil (Moustafa *et al.*, 2023), due to the function of microorganisms found in vermicompost that work or break organic matter down into the proteins, starches, and sugars of humus. According to Sharma and Verma, (2011) organic carbon significantly increased in the

rhizosphere soil due to rhizobium inoculation and VC application over the control; likewise, the experimental report of Fall *et al.*, (2016) revealed a significant increment of soil organic carbon due to rhizobium inoculation. This might be due to the function of root exudates, which are recognized as a vital communication system between plants and microbial communities populating the rhizosphere (Sugiyama *et al.*,2007), and it is a mix of a wide variety of compounds, including primary and secondary metabolites, carbohydrates, amino acids, and organic acids, which are secreted in larger quantities and also add organic carbon to the soil (Reddy *et al.*, 2020).

Table 8: Interaction effect of phosphorus with vermicompost application on organic Carbon

P rate(kgha-1)	OC (%)		
	VC rate(t ha-1)		
	0	2.5	5
0	1.25 ^e	1.42 ^{bc}	1.47 ^b
30	1.28 ^{de}	1.36 ^{cd}	1.47 ^b
60	1.29 ^{de}	1.36 ^{cd}	1.61 ^a
LSD (< 0.05)	0.0903		
P*VC	0.0298		
CV (%)	5.53		

Mean values within a columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at $P \leq 0.05$; CV= Coefficient of variation; VC=vermicompost

The interaction effect of 60kg ha⁻¹ with 5t ha⁻¹ VC results the highest 1.61% OC in the soil. This result agreed with that of Karmakar *et al.*, (2015) report which found higher value of organic carbon from integrated application of VC with chemical fertilizer, thus improved soil organic carbon might be obtained due to the content of vermicompost with high organic matter, humus and essential nutrients in the soil, in addition vermicompost served as a reservoir of different types of nutrients and contains micro sites rich in available carbon and nitrogen (Shirani *et al.*, 2002).

Cation exchange capacity (CEC)

The CEC of soil after harvest was significantly affected by the main effects and by the two-way interaction effect of phosphorus rate with VC application, whereas the other interaction effect was non-significant on this parameter.

Table 9: Interaction effect of phosphorus with vermicompost application on soil CEC and phosphorus

P rate(kgha-1)	CEC cmol (+) kg-1			Avail. P (mg/kg)		
	VC rate(t ha-1)			VC rate(t ha-1)		
	0	2.5	5	0	2.5	5
0	9.85 ^e	12.04 ^{cd}	14.28 ^a	3.23 ^e	4.15 ^{de}	4.21 ^{de}
30	12.07 ^{cd}	12.22 ^c	13.92 ^{ab}	6.85 ^c	5.50 ^{cd}	5.42 ^d
60	9.99 ^e	10.94 ^{de}	12.79 ^{bc}	14.12 ^a	9.13 ^b	9.06 ^b
LSD (< 0.05)	1.1968			1.418		
P*VC	0.0227			<.0001		
CV (%)	9.03			17.64		

Mean values within a columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at $P \leq 0.05$; CV= Coefficient of variation; VC=vermicompost

The highest soil CEC (14.28 cmol (+) kg⁻¹) was obtained from the interaction effect of 0kg ha⁻¹ P with 5tha⁻¹ VC, followed by the interaction effect of 30kg ha⁻¹ P with 5tha⁻¹ VC, which obtained 13.92 cmol (+) kg⁻¹, while the lowest CEC (9.85 cmol (+) kg⁻¹) was obtained from the control treatment. In agreement with this result, (Perkins, 1958) a significant improvement in soil CEC due to the integrated effect of vermicompost application and NPS rate. Increasing the application of vermicompost significantly improves soil CEC (Bekele *et al.*, 2018). This outcome may have been obtained as a result of the activity of microorganisms that break down organic matter, raising soil CEC as a result of increased vermicompost application (Alkobaisy and Mutlag, 2021). Soil CEC typically increases as clay content and organic matter in the soil increase because cation exchange occurs on surfaces of clay minerals, organic matter, and roots (Demir, 2019). The highest CEC may be attained due to VC application because vermicompost is an organic amendment and contains most nutrients in plant-available forms, including phosphates, exchangeable K, exchangeable Mg, and exchangeable Ca; thus, the increase in soil CEC over the control could be directly attributed to the increase in soil organic matter brought on due to the increasing application of vermicompost (Manivannan *et al.*, 2009). Phosphorus fertilization and vermicompost application improve soil organic carbon (Karmakar *et al.*, 2015) and (Ortas and Bykova, 2020) . Furthermore, organic carbon provides more exchange sites and raises soil CEC because soil organic carbon has significant impacts on the enhancement of the cation exchange

capacity of soils (Ramos *et al.*, 2018). In addition, Perkins, (1958) reported that the CEC of soil increases due to phosphorus application.

Exchangeable soil Ca, Mg, Na, K

Exchangeable Ca was significantly affected by the main effect rhizobium inoculation, phosphorus application and by the two-way interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with VC application, while the effect of phosphorus rate and the other interaction effects show no-significant value.

Table 10: Interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with vermicompost on exchangeable soil Ca, Mg, Na

VC rate(t ha ⁻¹)	Ca cmol (+) kg-1		Mg cmol (+) kg-1		Na cmol (+) kg-1	
	Inoculated	Non-inoculated	Inoculated	Non-inoculated	Inoculated	Non-inoculated
0	5.67 ^b	5.51 ^b	0.58 ^b	0.49 ^c	0.22 ^{cd}	0.24 ^{bc}
2.5	5.67 ^b	5.87 ^b	0.58 ^b	0.51 ^c	0.25 ^b	0.26 ^b
5	6.38 ^a	5.66 ^b	0.65 ^a	0.47 ^c	0.21 ^d	0.29 ^a
LSD (< 0.05)	0.3971		0.0487		0.0263	
RH*VC	0.0077		0.009		0.0012	
CV (%)	7.15		9.34		10.73	

Mean values within a columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at P≤0.05; CV= Coefficient of variation; VC=vermicompost

The highest exchangeable Ca (6.38 cmol (+) kg⁻¹) was obtained from the interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with 5tha⁻¹VC application, whereas the control treatment obtained the lowest (5.51 cmol (+) kg⁻¹), in agreement with this, Mahmoud and Ibrahim, (2012) reported a significant increase of Ca in soil due to VC application. This has resulted because vermicompost can contain more Ca than topsoil, and soils with compost applications tend to develop high concentrations of nutrients such as ammonium, calcium, magnesium, potassium, and sodium. Contrary to this, Ram *et al.*, (2021)reported the non-significant effect of vermicompost application on soil Ca. The experimental result of Omeke, (2017) revealed that rhizobium inoculation results in higher exchangeable cations than non-inoculated soil in a trial done on sandy loam soil.

Exchangeable soil Mg was significantly affected by rhizobium inoculation, by the main factor VC application, and by the two-way interaction (rhizobium inoculation with VC application), while the other interactions are non-significant. The interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with VC application shows an increasing value of exchangeable magnesium compared with VC application without rhizobium inoculation. The interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with 5tha⁻¹VC application shows a 24.62% higher value than the control and obtains (0.65 cmol (+) kg⁻¹) exchangeable Mg. Exchangeable Na was very highly significantly ($p = <.0001$) and significantly ($p = 0.0152$) affected by the main factor (rhizobium inoculation and VC application), respectively, and by the two-way interaction (rhizobium inoculation and VC application) effect, while the main effect phosphorus rate and the other interaction effects are non-significant. The highest (0.29 cmol (+) kg⁻¹) exchangeable Na in soil was obtained from 5tha⁻¹VC application with non-rhizobium inoculated treatment.

Exchangeable K was highly significantly affected by the main effects and by the two-way interaction (rhizobium inoculation with VC application), and is highly significantly affected by the three-way interaction; however, phosphorus application and the other two-way interaction effects were non-significant in this parameter.

The highest exchangeable K (1.42 cmol (+) kg⁻¹) was obtained from the interaction effect of rhizobium with 5tha⁻¹VC and 0 kg ha⁻¹P followed by the interaction effect of rhizobium with 5tha⁻¹VC and 60 kg ha⁻¹P, while the lowest (1.05 cmol (+) kg⁻¹) exchangeable K was obtained from the control, this result of exchangeable K in the soil was ranged as high according to rating by FAO, (2006). Overall, rhizobium inoculation significantly increases exchangeable K in the soil compared to non-inoculation. A similar result by Chimdi et al., (2022) was reported on the increasing effect of rhizobium inoculation on basic cations; likewise, the report of Sharma and Verma, (2011) revealed that the interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation farmyard manure and fertilizer significantly increases exchangeable K in the soil, and similar to the result of this experiment, their result also showed a higher result of K in the soil during rhizobium inoculation unlike the non-inoculated one; likewise, Alkobaisy and Mutlag, (2021) reported a significantly higher value of exchangeable K by the integrated application of rhizobium vermicompost and fertilizer. Exchangeable K increases as the application rate of VC increases from 0tha⁻¹ VC to 5t ha⁻¹ VC, along with this, Bekele *et al.*, (2018) reported the significant effect of VC application on

exchangeable soil K, which might be obtained due to the released potassium in the soil from vermicompost application.

Table 11: interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation, phosphorus and VC application rates on soil exchangeable potassium

K cmol (+) kg-1				
RH	P rate(kgha-1)	VC rate(t ha-1)		
		0	2.5	5
Inoculated	0	1.16 ^{fgh}	1.23 ^{de}	1.42 ^a
	30	1.22 ^{defg}	1.22 ^{def}	1.31 ^{bc}
	60	1.06 ^{ij}	1.24 ^{de}	1.33 ^b
Non-inoculated	0	1.05 ^j	1.13 ^{hi}	1.22 ^{def}
	30	1.08 ^{ij}	1.15 ^{gh}	1.25 ^{cd}
	60	1.15 ^{fgh}	1.17 ^{efgh}	1.27 ^{bcd}
	LSD (< 0.05)	0.0726		
	RH*P*VC	0.0087		
	CV (%)	3.63		

Mean values within a columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at $P \leq 0.05$; CV= Coefficient of variation; VC=vermicompost

4.3. Rhizobium inoculation, phosphorus and vermicompost application effect on biological nitrogen fixation

Total plant nitrogen, amount of fixed nitrogen, and %Ndfa was very highly significantly ($p < .0001$) affected by the main effects (rhizobium inoculation, vermicompost, and P application). The two-way interaction (Rhizobium inoculation with P application) highly significantly and significantly affected total plant nitrogen, fixed nitrogen, and %Ndfa respectively. Also, the other two-way interaction (rhizobium inoculation with vermicompost) significantly affected total plant nitrogen and fixed nitrogen, and the three-way interaction was not significant.

Table 12: Effect Rhizobium inoculation, phosphorus and vermicompost on common bean biological nitrogen fixation

		Total N yield(kg ha ⁻¹)	Fixed-N (kg ha ⁻¹)	% NDFA
Rhizobium	Inoculated	107.98 ^a	48.85 ^a	43.24 ^a
	Non-inoculated	98.25 ^b	39.77 ^b	37.69 ^b
	LSD	2.7221	2.7202	1.9758
	P value	<.0001	<.0001	<.0001
P rate(kgha-1)	0	82.41 ^c	25.9 ^b	30.15 ^b
	30	116.22 ^a	55.85 ^a	47.38 ^a
	60	110.71 ^b	55.72 ^a	47.25 ^a
	LSD	3.3339	3.3316	2.4199
	P value	<.0001	<.0001	<.0001
VC rate(t ha-1)	0	95.14 ^b	37.85 ^b	30.85 ^b
	2.5	96.52 ^b	39.52 ^b	38.42 ^b
	5	111.68 ^a	53.03 ^a	46.53 ^a
	LSD	3.8584	3.3316	2.4199
	P value	<.0001	<.0001	<.0001
	CV (%)	4.77	10.97	8.59

Mean values within a columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at $P \leq 0.05$; NS= non-significant; CV= Coefficient of variation; VC=vermicompost

The highest amount of total plant nitrogen, fixed nitrogen, and %Ndfa was obtained from inoculation (107.98 kg ha⁻¹), (48.85 kg ha⁻¹), and (43.24%), whereas the lowest result was

recorded from non-inoculated one. In agreement with this result, the experimental finding of Samago *et al.*, (2018) shows the highest %Ndfa due to rhizobium inoculation in an experiment done in sandy-loam soil, as well Raji *et al.*, (2019) also reported significantly higher amount of fixed nitrogen from inoculation of rhizobium on haricot bean compared to non-inoculated haricot beans. Similarly, Makgato *et al.*, (2020) reported the effect of inoculation on increasing atmospheric fixation. This might have resulted because inoculated Rhizobium on the seed of a haricot bean is capable of fixing atmospheric nitrogen more easily than the non-inoculated ones (Bliss and Hardson, 1993), and the effective symbiotic relation of inoculant and host crop tends to accelerate plant nitrogen uptake %Ndfa (Unkovich *et al.*, 2008).

The highest value of total plant nitrogen (111.68kg ha⁻¹), fixed nitrogen (53.03kg ha⁻¹) and %Ndfa (46.53) was obtained from the application rate of 5t ha⁻¹ VC, while the lowest recorded from the control treatment (Table 12), in agreement with this, (Al-Chammaa *et al.*, 2014) reported a significant increase in the value of %Ndfa and the amount of N₂-fixed by the soybean due to sheep manure application rate. The reason behind this result might be due to the nitrogenase activity in the soil rhizosphere, which is promoted by the addition of adequate vermicompost in the soil that helps nitrogen fixation in legumes.

The application rate of phosphorus significantly increases atmospheric nitrogen fixation by haricot bean. The highest total plant nitrogen (116.22kg ha⁻¹) fixed nitrogen and %Ndfa (55.85kg ha⁻¹) and (47.38%) were obtained from application rate of 30 kg ha⁻¹ P, while the lowest values were recorded from the control treatment. However application rate of 30 kg ha⁻¹ P and 60 kg ha⁻¹ P obtains statistically similar result, in agreement with this experiment, (Kellman, 2008) reported a significant result of phosphorus application on atmospheric N₂-fixation, similarly Siyeni, (2016) found increasing nitrogen fixation due to the increasing application effect of phosphorus on soybean. This might be due to the influences of phosphorus on nodule development through its basic functions in plants as an energy source and enhance N₂-fixation; also, sufficient application of P for legumes enhances root growth, the process of photosynthesis, translocation of sugars, and other such functions which directly or indirectly influence N fixation by legume plants. Contrary to the result of this experiment, Chinke *et al.*, (2022) reported a non-significant effect of phosphorus application on the yield of fixed nitrogen and %Ndfa; however, according to their report, P application results higher amount of fixed nitrogen from the atmosphere

Table 13: Interaction effect of Rhizobium inoculation with Phosphorus rate on common bean biological nitrogen fixation

P rate(t ha-1)	Total N yield (kg ha ⁻¹)		Fixed-N (kg ha ⁻¹)		% NDFA	
	Inoculate d	Non-inoculated	Inoculate d	Non-inoculated	Inoculate d	Non-inoculated
0	86.23 ^d	78.6 ^e	29.72 ^d	22.09 ^e	33.61 ^d	26.69 ^e
30	126.48 ^a	105.96 ^c	66.18 ^a	45.59 ^c	52.04 ^a	42.72 ^c
60	111.24 ^b	110.19 ^{bc}	53.25 ^b	52.18 ^{b6}	47.61 ^b	46.84 ^b
LSD (< 0.05)	4.7149		4.7116		3.4222	
RH*P	0.0005		0.0004		0.0032	
CV (%)	4.77		10.97		8.59	

Mean values within a columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at $P \leq 0.05$; CV= Coefficient of variation

The highest amount of total nitrogen (126.48 kg ha⁻¹) fixed nitrogen (66.18 kg ha⁻¹) and %Ndfa (52.04%) was obtained from the interaction effect of inoculation with 30 kg ha⁻¹ P rate, whereas the lowest result was obtained from the control (Table:13); the overall result of the interaction effect shows that inoculation with Phosphorus rate obtains highest amount of fixed nitrogen and %Ndfa compared to the non-inoculated treatments.in agreement with this (Abbasi et al.,2010) reported the significant increment of total N uptake and nitrogen fixation due to the interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation and phosphorus level. The application rate of phosphorus in P deficient soil improves the N₂-fixation and grain yield (Al-Chammaa., 2014). This could be due to the phosphorus impact on nodule growth through its fundamental roles as an energy source in plants (Samago et al.,2018)and adequate P enhance root growth, photosynthesis, sugar transport and other processes either directly or indirectly affects legume plants to fix nitrogen (Tarik et al., 2018) ,due to this reason phosphorus application plays significant role in the symbiotic performance of rhizobium and legume growth improvement (Raji et al,2019).

Table 14: Interaction Effect of Rhizobium inoculation with vermicompost on common bean biological nitrogen fixation

VC rate(t ha ⁻¹)	Total N yield (kg ha ⁻¹)		Fixed-N (kg ha ⁻¹)	
	Inoculated	Non-inoculated	Inoculated	Non-inoculated
0	104.04 ^c	89.36 ^d	46.24 ^c	31.48 ^d
2.5	101.82 ^c	93.86 ^d	43.51 ^b	35.52 ^d
5	118.09 ^a	111.54 ^b	59.41 ^a	52.81 ^b
LSD (< 0.05)	4.7149		4.7116	
RH*VC	0.0008		0.0423	
CV (%)	4.77		10.97	

Mean values within a columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at $P \leq 0.05$; CV= Coefficient of variation; VC=vermicompost

The interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with vermicompost application significantly affects plant total nitrogen ($p=0.0008$) amount of fixed nitrogen ($p=0.0423$), however, %Ndfa was non-significant. The interaction effect of inoculation with 5t ha⁻¹ VC results the highest (118.09 kg ha⁻¹ and 59.41 kg ha⁻¹) total plant nitrogen and fixed nitrogen respectively from the atmosphere, followed by the interaction effect of 5t ha⁻¹ VC without inoculation, while the lowest total plant nitrogen and fixed nitrogen (89.36 kg ha⁻¹ and 33.27 kg ha⁻¹), respectively was obtained from the control.

The highest mean value (126.67 kg ha⁻¹, 66.9 kg ha⁻¹ and 52.46%) of total plant nitrogen, fixed nitrogen, and %Ndfa, respectively, were obtained from the interaction effect of 5t ha⁻¹ VC with 30kg ha⁻¹ P, followed by the result of 60kg ha⁻¹ P with 5t ha⁻¹ VC application which is 121.81 kg ha⁻¹, 63.69 kg ha⁻¹ and 52.20% respectively, while the lowest total plant nitrogen (95.95 kg ha⁻¹), fixed nitrogen (15.78 kg ha⁻¹) and %Ndfa (22.48 %) was obtained from control treatment. The reducing value of total plant nitrogen, fixed nitrogen and %Ndfa as a result of adding 60kg ha⁻¹ P fertilizer, could illustrate that plant's P demands had been satisfied and no need for further P addition. The application rate of 30kg ha⁻¹ P could be sufficient amount in order to achieve the maximum N yield in the experimental area, in addition, VC addition led to a further considerable increase in the amount of plant N uptake and nitrogen fixation, This might be due to the greater microbial biomass obtained during the application of organic matter; high microbial biomass carbon was reflected in a greater N mineralization and N uptake by plants, in addition to the

significant organic N contribution from the manure and from fixed nitrogen, in agreement with this result (Al-Chammaa *et al.*, 2014), shows the increasing effect of phosphorus application and sheep manure on the total nitrogen yield of soya bean and %Ndfa.

Table 15: Interaction Effect of Phosphorus with vermicompost on common bean biological nitrogen fixation

P rate(kgha-1)	Total-N yiled (kg ha ⁻¹)			Fixed-N (kg ha ⁻¹)			%Ndfa		
	VC rate(t ha-1)			VC rate(t ha-1)			VC rate(t ha-1)		
	0	2.5	5	0	2.5	5	0	2.5	5
0	69.58 ^f	81.72 ^e	95.95 ^d	15.78 ^f	24.1 ^e	37.83 ^d	22.48 ^e	28.84 ^d	39.13 ^c
30	113.63 ^b	108.37 ^{bc}	126.67 ^a	51.98 ^b	48.77 ^{bc}	66.9 ^a	44.92 ^b	44.76 ^b	52.46 ^a
60	106.9 ^c	103.43 ^c	121.81 ^a	48.79 ^{bc}	45.68 ^c	63.69 ^b	45.35 ^b	44.13 ^b	52.20 ^a
LSD (< 0.05)	5.7745			5.7705			4.1914		
P*VC	<.0001			<.0001			<.0001		
CV (%)	5.63			14.42			7.73		

Mean values within a columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at P≤0.05; CV= Coefficient of variation; VC=vermicompost

4.4. Effect of Rhizobium Inoculation and Vermi-compost application on growth Parameters of Haricot bean

4.4.1. Days to 50% flowering

The main effects (phosphorus rate, vermicompost), the two-way interaction (rhizobium inoculation with phosphorus rate, rhizobium inoculation with vermicompost, phosphorus rate with vermicompost application), and the three-way interaction effect (rhizobium inoculation with phosphorus application and vermicompost application) resulted in a significant effect on the number of days to set 50% flower, while the main effect of rhizobium inoculation didn't show a significant effect on this parameter.

The minimum (44.67) days to 50% flowering were recorded from the application rate of 60kg ha⁻¹ with the absent of rhizobium inoculation and vermicompost application, followed by the interaction effect if rhizobium inoculation with 60kg ha⁻¹ and 2.5t ha⁻¹ which is 45 days. This might be due to the effect of phosphorus in the early growth (it is one of the main basic nutrients for plant growth) and stimulates plant root development and helps the plant access other soil minerals and water easily during its early growth stage. In agreement with this Paulos *et al.*, (2018) and Chimdi *et al.*, (2022) experiments on different rate of phosphorus effect on the growth of haricot bean shows the lowest days to flowering as well, Negash et al,(2020) also reported the fastest days to flowering from the interaction effect of Rhizobium inoculation and phosphorus rate. However, the longest days to 50% flowering was recorded from the interaction effect of Rhizobium inoculation with 5t ha⁻¹ vermicompost, this might be due to the slow release of nutrients from vermicompost in the early growth stage, which shows delayed flowering time compared to the other treatment in agreement to this result Tadese, (2017)obtained the longest flowering days from the interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation and vermicompost application on haricot bean.

Table 16: Interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with phosphorus and vermicompost on Days to 50% flowering

RH	P rate(kg ha ⁻¹)	Days to 50% flowering			
		VC rate(t ha ⁻¹)	0	2.5	5
Inoculated	0		46.67 ^{efgh}	48.67 ^{bc}	50.33 ^a
	30		47.33 ^{cdef}	47 ^{defg}	46.33 ^{fghi}
	60		45.67 ^{ghij}	45.00 ^{ij}	45.67 ^{ghij}
Non-inoculated	0		45.33 ^{hij}	45.33 ^{hij}	49.00 ^{ab}
	30		45.67 ^{ghij}	47.67 ^{bcdef}	47.33 ^{cdef}
	60		44.67 ^j	48.33 ^{bcd}	48.00 ^{bcde}
	LSD (< 0.05)		1.5844		
	RH*P*VC		0.006		
	CV (%)		2.04		

Mean values within a columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at P≤0.05; CV= Coefficient of variation; VC=vermicompost

4.4.2. Days to 90% physiological maturity

Days to physiological maturity was highly significantly ($P = 0.0001$) affected by the main effects of rhizobium inoculation and VC application, while rhizobium inoculation shows a non-significant effect on days to physiological maturity. In addition, the two-way interaction (rhizobium with phosphorus rate, rhizobium inoculation with VC application, and phosphorus rate with VC application) and three-way interaction (rhizobium inoculation, phosphorus rate, and VC application) effect show a significant effect on this parameter.

Physiological maturity of haricot bean shows the shortest days from the interaction effect of non-rhizobium inoculation with 60kg ha^{-1} P rate 0tha^{-1} VC application. similar result by Meleta and Abera, (2019) was reported that the increasing effect of phosphorus level significantly reduced the number of days to physiological maturity, this might be due to the fact that phosphorus application enhances the early growth and physiological maturity of haricot by facilitating cell division and good root system to ensuring timely and uniform ripening of the crop (Alemu et al., 2018), P is needed most by young, fast-growing tissues, which is suitable for early maturity of legumes (Tarik Mitran et al., 2018). In addition (Gidago et al., 2011) also reported reduced days to 90% physiological maturity as the application rate of phosphorus increase, contrary to this result delayed day to 90% physiological maturity was reported by Negash et al., (2020) due to rate of phosphorus application. According to the finding of this experiment the interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation, application of 2.5tha^{-1} and 60kg ha^{-1} P rate resulted the longest (88) days to physiological maturity. This might be resulted due to the fixation of nitrogen by the rhizobium strain which is inoculated in the seed might have promoted vegetative growth of the crop, and slows physiological maturity and pod filling, as well might be due to the lower nutrient application by the VC rate, because these level of VC might not be enough for plant growth and maturity; hence the combined effect of those treatments might let led to prolonged days to physiological maturity. these result is similar with the finding of Birhanu, (2020) on the prolonged days physiological maturity of faba bean due to rhizobium inoculation and VC application.

Table 17: Interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with phosphorus and vermicompost on Days to 90% physiological maturity

Days to 90% physiological maturity				
RH	P rate(kgha-1)	VC rate(t ha-1)		
		0	2.5	5
Inoculated	0	85.33 ^{def}	86.67 ^{bc}	86.33 ^{bcd}
	30	85.33 ^{def}	86 ^{bcd}	85.33 ^{def}
	60	83.67 ^h	88 ^a	86.67 ^{bc}
Non-inoculated	0	84.33 ^{fgh}	83.33 ^h	87.00 ^{ab}
	30	84.00 ^{gh}	85.67 ^{cde}	85.00 ^{efg}
	60	81.00 ⁱ	85.67 ^{cde}	85.00 ^{efg}
LSD (< 0.05)		2.3903		
RH*P*VC		1.2501		
CV (%)		1.5		

Mean values within a columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at $P \leq 0.05$; CV= Coefficient of variation; VC=vermicompost

4.4.3. Leaf number and leaf area index

Leaf Number was significantly affected ($p=0.0103$) by the main effect Rhizobium inoculation and is very highly significantly affected by phosphorus application ($p=0.0003$) and vermicompost application ($p=0.0008$), while there is no significant variation by their interaction effect on this parameter.

Rhizobium inoculation obtains the highest leaf number (14.96) compared to (14.33) which is obtained from non-inoculated treatment. In line with the result of this experiment, the finding of Sajid et al., (2011) also reported the highest number of leaf due to inoculation over the non-inoculated one. This might be due to the addition of nitrogen by the inoculated rhizobium bacteria's through fixation (Hasan, 2018). As it was stated by Gebrehana and Dagnaw, (2020) nitrogen enhance the vegetative growth of plant, the presence of more and adequate number of leaf ameliorates the photosynthesis rate of the plant which is the main mechanism of the plant system these means rhizobium inoculation increases the main Supporter and responsible

component of plant for growth and productivity due to the additional supply of nitrogen from fixation.

The rate of phosphorus application was significantly increases number of haricot bean leaf in contrast to the control. The highest number of leaf (15.34) was obtained from the application rate of 30kg ha⁻¹ P followed by the application rate of 60kg ha⁻¹ P which obtains (15.01) number of leafs (table5) and the lowest number of leaf (14.03) was recorded from control. In line with this Kassa, (2014) reported the increasing effect of leaf number from increasing level of phosphorus application at Wolaita.

Application rate of 5t ha⁻¹ VC significantly increased number of leaf compared to other treatments with 15.17 numbers of leafs, VC promotes the vegetative growth and leaf number of plants (Seenan *et al.*, 2018),this might be due to the symbiotic relationship of rhizobium (bacteria) with the roots of leguminous crops, which fix atmospheric nitrogen into the roots of haricot bean and enhances the growth, and amount of leaf number which helps in feeding bean seeds. Similarly, Thuy *et al.* (2017) reported the significant increment of leaf number due to the application level of VC.

Table 18:-Effect of Rhizobium Inoculation phosphorus rate and Vermicompost application on growth Parameters of Haricot bean

		leaf number	LAI	Plant height (cm)	Number of branches per plant
Rhizobium	Inoculated	14.96 ^a	2.82 ^a	48.53 ^a	4.22 ^a
	Non-inoculated	14.33 ^b	2.54 ^b	44.71 ^b	3.96 ^b
	LSD	0.4708	0.0984	1.7139	0.1203
	P value	0.0103	0.0001	<.0001	0.0001
P rate (kg ha⁻¹)	0	14.03 ^c	2.7	45.43 ^b	3.91 ^b
	30	15.34 ^a	2.65	46.05 ^b	4.2 ^a
	60	15.01 ^b	2.69	48.21 ^a	4.1 ^a
	LSD	0.3078	NS	0.9812	0.0768
	P value	0.0003	0.7069	0.0317	0.0004
VC rate (t ha⁻¹)	0	14.12 ^b	2.64	46.60 ^b	3.93 ^b
	2.5	14.74 ^{a^b}	2.73	43.05 ^c	3.82 ^b
	5	15.17 ^a	2.68	50.21 ^a	4.5 ^a

LSD	0.5766	NS	2.0991	0.1473
P value	0.0008	0.2896	<.0001	<.0001
CV (%)	5.8	6.64	6.65	5.53

Mean values within a columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at $P \leq 0.05$; NS= non-significant; CV= Coefficient of variation; VC=vermi-compost

LAI was highly significantly affected by the main effect rhizobium inoculation ($P= 0.0001$) and by the two-way interaction (VC with phosphorus) ($P= 0.0084$, while the other main effects and interaction effects didn't show any significant difference on this parameter.

The highest LAI (2.83) was obtained from the interaction effect of $5t\ ha^{-1}$ VC with $0kg\ ha^{-1}$ P rate, followed by the interaction effect of $2.5t\ ha^{-1}$ VC with $60kg\ ha^{-1}$ P which resulted (2.80) while the lowest LAI (2.51) was recorded from control (Table:19). This result was supported by Manivannan *et al.*, (2009) on application of vermicompost in combination with chemical fertilizer which resulted in a larger leaf area index. Also, the report of Pandiyan *et al.*, (2020) shows the increasing result of LAI due to VC application. Vermicompost contain higher amount of nitrogen in line with other essential nutrients (Mahmoud and Gad, 2020),so far the nitrogen and other nutrients found in vermicompost helps the plant to increase the vegetative growth and leaf area index of plant. Increase in LAI might be due to the amount of available N, Mg, Ca, P, K and other essential nutrients which contained in vermicompost which improved the vegetative growth and the application of phosphorus which is important in nucleotide-based metabolic processes and the result of this integrate d application could help in increasing cell division and expansion of leaf an vegetative growth and results an increase in LAI (Tadesse et al., 2022).

4.4.4. Plant height

Plant height was significantly affected by the main effects (Rhizobium inoculation phosphorus rate and VC application) and by the two-way interaction (phosphorus rate and VC application), while the other interaction effect didn't significantly affect plant height.

The highest (48.53cm) height of haricot bean was recorded from rhizobium inoculation compared to the non-inoculated (44.71cm) one ,the increase in haricot bean height might be due to the additional fixed nitrogen from the atmosphere because of seed inoculation which plays vital roles for the vegetative growth of plant, as well the availability of nutrient nitrogen, stimulates the growth of internode length and improves plant height (Togay *et al.*, 2008). In

agreement with the result of this experiment Geleta and Bekele, (2022) reported the top faba bean plant height from rhizobium inoculation, similarly the finding of Sajid et al., (2011) shows the highest height of groundnut from rhizobium inoculation.

The interaction effect of 60kg ha⁻¹ P and 5t ha⁻¹ VC obtains the highest (50.63cm) plant height followed by the interaction effect of 0kg ha⁻¹ P and 5t ha⁻¹ VC which is (50.63cm), indeed both interaction effects shows statistically similar result, this increasing effect of plant height as level of VC rate increases might be due to the function of nutrients found in vermicompost which improves the vegetative growth of plants (Thuy *et al.*, 2017). Indeed the highest plant height by increasing rate of phosphorus This might be due to the function of phosphorus on plants in boosting root growth, encouraging tillering, and accelerating maturity (Mobasser and Branch, 2014). This result was supported by Alkobaisy and Mutlag, (2021)who found the highest height of mung bean by the interaction effect of VC and chemical fertilizer compared to the control. Height of haricot bean shows significant increase due to phosphorus application in experiment done on andisols, with textural class of silty loam (Sigay et al.,2020). Contrary to this result, on an experiment done at Areka, Wolaita on textural class of clay soil shows the non-significant effect of phosphorus application and results decreased plant height as rate of phosphorus increases (Gidago et al., (2011).

Table 19: Interaction effect of phosphorus and Vermi-compost on LAI and leaf number of Haricot bean

P rate(kgha-1)	Plant height			Leaf area index			Number of branch		
				VC rate(t ha-1)			VC rate(t ha-1)		
	0	2.5	5	0	2.5	5	0	2.5	5
0	43.74 ^{cd}	41.95 ^d	50.63 ^a	2.48 ^c	2.70 ^{ab}	2.83 ^a	3.60 ^f	3.93 ^{de}	4.23 ^{bc}
30	48.10 ^{ab}	40.76 ^d	49.32 ^{ab}	2.76 ^{ab}	2.72 ^{ab}	2.59 ^{bc}	4.17 ^{bcd}	3.70 ^{ef}	4.87 ^a
60	47.77 ^{ab}	45.84 ^{bc}	50.67 ^a	2.66 ^{abcd}	2.76 ^{ab}	2.63 ^{abc}	3.93 ^{de}	4.00 ^{cd}	4.40 ^b
LSD (< 0.05)	1.5885			0.2087			0.2551		
P*VC	0.0426			0.0126			0.0001		
CV (%)	6.3			6.64			5.31		

Mean values within a columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at P≤0.05; CV= Coefficient of variation; VC=vermi-compost

4.4.5. Number of branches per plant

Number of branch per plant was very highly significantly affected by the main effects (rhizobium inoculation, phosphorus rate and VC application) and by the two-way interaction (phosphorus rate and VC application), while the other interaction shows non-significant effect on this parameter.

Rhizobium inoculation results the highest (4.22) number of branches compared to the non-inoculated one (3.96). In agreement with this result Tehulie, (2020) reported the highest number of branch due to the effect of rhizobium inoculation. The uppermost number of branch by rhizobium inoculation might be due to the effect of Nitrogen from biological Nitrogen fixation which promotes rapid vegetative growth and additional branch formation. Comparable finding by (Birhanu, 2020) showed that the number of faba bean branches were increased due to inoculation of rhizobium. In addition Miriko, (2018) also reported the significant growth of branch due to rhizobium inoculation. Application rate of 30kg ha⁻¹ P results the highest (4.21) number of haricot bean branch, whereas the lowest (3.91) branch number was recorded from the control treatment, this result was supported by the experimental finding of Kassa, (2014) on the response of haricot bean varieties to phosphorus levels showed the increasing number of branch as application rate of phosphorus increases. Similarly, Zebire and Gelgelo, (2019) also reported the significant effect of phosphorus application on increasing the number of haricot bean branches. The increasing number of branches along with the application rate of phosphorus could be due to the activity of phosphorus on cell division and on development of new tissue.

Highest number of branch (4.5) was recorded from the application rate of 5t ha⁻¹ VC (table18). The report of Pandiyan *et al.*, (2020) showed that VC application significantly increased branch number of plants. This might be due to the effect of essential nutrients like nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium and other secondary and supplementary nutrients in VC that accelerates the growth of crops; as well it might be due to the function of VC in promoting more water holding capacity of soil when added in to soil, so that the rhizosphere of the plant alleviate water stress more than non-VC applied soils.

The interaction effect of phosphorus rate and vermicompost application shows 26.09% and 18.18% higher number of branch over the control by the interaction effect of 30 kg ha⁻¹ P with 5t ha⁻¹ P and 60 kg ha⁻¹ P with 2.5t ha⁻¹ VC respectively with its maximum result (4.87) and (4.40) branches, while lowest (3.60) branch number was recorded from control (Table: 19). The increasing number of branch might be due to optimum application of phosphorus which used for enhancement of nodule formation and increases N₂-fixation, increased leaf size and branching (Mebrahtu et al, 2021). In the same way, vermicompost promotes nitrogenase activity in the soil rhizosphere enhancing nitrogen fixation in legume, and improve the growth and yield of plants (Darzi *et al.*, 2012). VC also plays important role through creating suitable growth media for plant with high porosity, aeration, water-holding capacity, low C:N ratio and with important plant nutrients (Seenan *et al.*, 2018).

4.5. Effect of Rhizobium Inoculation, phosphorus rate and VC application on yield and yield components of Haricot bean

4.5.1. Number of pods per plant

Number of pods was very highly significantly ($p < .0001$) affected by the main effects (rhizobium inoculation, phosphorus rate and VC application) and by the two-way interaction effect (phosphorus rate with VC application), however the other interaction effects show non-significant result.

Rhizobium inoculation showed the highest number of pods (17.70) per plant compared to the non-inoculated one, which is (16.07), in agreement with this Sajid et al., (2011) stated plant pod number increases as a result of rhizobium inoculation. This result might be observed due to the effectiveness of inoculation over native soil Rhizobium and might leads for the production of more leaves through the addition of nitrogen through symbiotic nitrogen fixation, which enables the plant to have more photosynthesis rate and sink carbohydrates to the lower parts and promote the production of more pods. Similarly, Tehulie (2020) had also reported significant response of pod number to rhizobium inoculation on haricot bean, unlike with result of this experiment, non-significant effect of inoculation was reported by Abera and Abebe, (2018) and Nawaz *et al.*, (2017) on pod number of field pea and check pea respectively.

The highest number of pod (18.14) were obtained from the application of 30 kg ha⁻¹ P, while the lowest (16.05) number of pod were recorded from the control treatment ,in agreement with this Paulos, (2018) reported that the increasing rate of phosphorus application show significant rise in

number of pods per plant. Similarly, (Zebire and Gelgelo, 2019) reported the increasing number of pod as rate of phosphorus application increases in an experiment done on sandy loam soil in south ommo zone. To the contrary Gidago et al., (2011) reported non-significant value of pod number of haricot bean to phosphorus application. The increment of pod per plant with Phosphorus application might be due to the function of P fertilizer in pod filling and promotes the formation of pod (Sigaye *et al.*, 2020).

Application of 5t ha⁻¹ VC significantly increased number of pods by 15.39% and 10.21% over the application rate of 2.5t ha⁻¹ VC and control respectively, with its highest (18.52) number of pods per plant. In line with this, Birhanu, (2020) reported the significant increment of faba bean pods as rate of VC application increase on an experiment done at northern shewa zone on textural class of clay soil. Similarly, Grzegorz *et al.*, (2021) report showed the significant effect of VC application on increasing pod number of peas. VC enhances the growth and yield of plants because it contains plant nutrients such as nitrogen, calcium, phosphorus, potassium, sulfur and other secondary macro and micro nutrients that are useful for plant growth and quality production (Olle, 2019), also due to the presence of biologically active plant growth-influencing substances in VC, which are growth regulators like auxins, gibberellins, cytokinins of microbial origin.

Table 20: Interaction effect of phosphorus with Vermicompost on pod number of Haricot bean

P rate(kgha-1)	Number of pod per plant		
	VC rate(t ha-1)		
	0	2.5	5
0	14.23 ^f	16.00 ^{def}	17.90 ^{bc}
30	18.67 ^{ab}	16.16 ^{de}	19.60 ^a
60	17.00 ^{cd}	14.96 ^{ef}	18.07 ^{abc}
LSD (< 0.05)	0.7554		
P*VC	0.0006		
CV (%)	6.55		

Mean values within a columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at P≤0.05; CV= Coefficient of variation; VC=vermi-compost

The interaction effect of 30kg ha⁻¹ P with 5t ha⁻¹ VC application significantly increases pod number by 27.4% in accordance to the control, which obtains (19.60) number of haricot bean pod followed by the interaction effect of 30kg ha⁻¹ P with 0t ha⁻¹ VC resulting (18.67) number of pod. Increasing number of haricot bean pod was obtained due to the integrated effect of vermicompost and phosphorus might be because vermicompost increases the availability of nutrients in the soil and makes them available to the plant either by dissolving the compounds of these elements and liberating them from the organic acids that it produces during decomposition or by releasing these elements from the vermicompost (Azarpour *et al.*,2012) and due to the adequate supply of phosphorus, which helps for better photosynthesis reaction and plant growth (Dejene et al., 2016).

Table 21: Effect of Rhizobium Inoculation, phosphorus rate and VC application on yield and yield components of Haricot bean

		Number of pods per plant	Number of seeds per pod	HSW(g)
Rhizobium	Inoculated	17.70 ^a	5.71 ^a	26.9
	Non-inoculated	16.07 ^b	5.38 ^b	26.87
	LSD	0.7085	0.1112	NS
	P value	<.0001	<.0001	0.7844
P rate(kgha-1)	0	16.05 ^b	5.30 ^b	26.38 ^b
	30	18.14 ^a	5.73 ^a	28.01 ^a
	60	17.00 ^a	5.69 ^a	26.36 ^b
	LSD	0.4771	0.1077	0.2888
	P value	<.0001	<.0001	<.0001
VC rate(t ha-1)	0	16.63 ^b	5.42 ^b	26.35 ^c
	2.5	15.67 ^b	5.54 ^{ab}	27.00 ^b
	5	18.52 ^a	5.67 ^a	27.51 ^a
	LSD	0.8677	0.1361	0.6065
	P value	<.0001	0.0036	0.0018
	CV (%)	7.59	3.62	3.33

Mean values within a columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at P≤0.05; NS= non-significant; CV= Coefficient of variation; VC=vermicompost; HSW=Hundred seed weight

4.5.2. Number of seeds per pod

Seed number was significantly affected by the main effects, by the two-ways and three-way interaction effects. The interaction effect of rhizobium, phosphorus rate and VC application significantly ($p=0.0117$) affects number of seed.

Table 22: Interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with phosphorus and VC application on seed number per pod of haricot bean

Number of seed per pod				
RH	P rate(kgha-1)	VC rate(t ha-1)		
		0	2.5	5
Inoculated	0	5.13 ^g	5.8 ^{bcde}	6.00 ^{abc}
	30	5.67 ^{cdef}	5.40 ^{fg}	6.2 ^a
	60	6.07 ^{ab}	5.53 ^{def}	5.6 ^{def}
Non-inoculated	0	4.00 ^h	5.40 ^{fg}	5.13 ^g
	30	5.87 ^{abcd}	5.53 ^{def}	5.6 ^{def}
	60	5.87 ^{abcd}	5.6 ^{def}	5.47 ^{efg}
LSD (< 0.05)		0.3335		
RH*P*VC		0.0117		
CV (%)		3.62		

Mean values within a columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at $P \leq 0.05$; CV= Coefficient of variation; VC=vermi-compost

Rhizobium inoculation with 30kg ha⁻¹ P rate and 5t ha⁻¹ VC shows 35.48% higher result compared to control, with 6.2 and 4 seeds per pod respectively. In agreement with this result Negash *et al.*, (2020) reported the highest number of seed per pod by the interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation and phosphorus application, the reason for higher number of seed per pod due to the integrated application of rhizobium with phosphorus and VC might be due to function of phosphorus in the transfer of energy which occurs in nodule functioning and protein synthesis and due to the influence of VC in encouraging the growth and effectiveness of microorganisms and their favorable effects on plant growth through the fixation of some elements like atmospheric nitrogen or by dissolving and releasing some of the precipitated or fixed elements like phosphorus. The enhancement of plant growth by the effect of VC to stimulates the

microbial activity of soil, increases the availability of oxygen, maintains normal soil temperature, increases soil porosity and infiltration of water, this creates a low oxygen environment within the nodule which allows Rhizobium bacteria to live and to fix N₂ (Darzi *et al.*, 2012) also having higher N₂-fixing ability bring enhanced rate of photosynthesis and growth improvement of plants (Birhanu, 2020), this results in greeter accumulation carbohydrate as starch in seed (Jeong *et al.*, 2018).

4.5.3. Hundred seed weight

Hundred seed weight of haricot bean was highly significantly affected by the main effects (phosphorus rate and VC application), by the two-way interactions (rhizobium inoculation with VC application) and (phosphorus rate with VC application) as well the three-ways interaction effect shows significant value in this parameter, however the main effect rhizobium inoculation and interaction effect of rhizobium with phosphorus didn't show significant difference.

Highest number of hundred seed (29.83) was obtained from the interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with 30kg ha⁻¹ and 2.5t ha⁻¹ VC, while the lowest (25.49) was recorded from control. In agreement with this result Tadese, (2017), reports significantly increasing result of HSW by the interaction effect of rhizobium with phosphorus rate and VC application. The increase in hundred seed weights due to the combined application of Rhizobium, phosphorus, and vermicompost might be due to the integrated supply of nutrients in the soil, which promotes leaf growth photosynthetic activity and increase assimilation to the storage organ, and resulting in the increase in hundred seed weights. In addition Argaw and Mnalku, (2017) reported the significant response of faba bean hundred seed weight due to rhizobium inoculation and level of VC application. To the contrary Darzi *et al.*, (2015) reported non-significant effect of rhizobium inoculation and VC application on HSW. similarly Debela *et al.*, (2021) also found the non-significant result of HSW of soya bean by rhizobium inoculation and VC level.

Table 23: Interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with phosphorus and VC application on HSW of haricot bean

		HSW(g)		
RH	P rate(kgha-1)	VC rate(t ha-1)		
		0	2.5	5
Inoculated	0	26.17 ^{fg}	26.38 ^{efg}	27.70 ^{cde}

	30	27.71 ^{cde}	25.59 ^{fg}	29.83 ^a
	60	26.8 ^{defg}	25.90 ^{fg}	25.93 ^{fg}
Non-inoculated	0	25.49 ^g	25.54 ^{fg}	27.0 ^{def}
	30	26.39 ^{efg}	29.38 ^{ab}	28.53 ^{abc}
	60	25.57 ^{fg}	27.89 ^{bcd}	26.06 ^{fg}
	LSD (< 0.05)	1.4855		
	RH*P*VC	0.0046		
	CV (%)	3.33		

Mean values within a columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at $P \leq 0.05$; CV= Coefficient of variation; VC=vermi-compost

4.5.4. Above ground dry biomass

Above ground dry biomass of haricot bean was very highly significantly affected ($P = < .0001$) by the main effects (rhizobium inoculation with phosphorus rate and VC application) and is highly significantly affected by the two-way interaction (rhizobium inoculation with phosphorus rate) and (phosphorus rate with VC application), while other interaction effects were non-significant.

Inoculation of rhizobium results the highest amount (3509 kg ha^{-1}) above ground dry biomass compared to the non-inoculated value (3311 kg ha^{-1}) (Table: 24).this result was in agreement with that of Gedamu et al., (2021) who reported a significant biomass yield of faba bean at south wollo. The increment of dry biomass due to rhizobium inoculation might be due to the addition of nitrogen through fixation of atmospheric nitrogen, through there symbiotic relation with the host plant (Adjei et al.,2006), due to this inoculated legumes can gain additional nitrogen over the non-inoculated one (Bado et al., 2018). Hence this additional nitrogen from N_2 -fixation promotes the vegetative growth and yield of haricot bean (Ndlovu et al.,2017). Similarly Amos and Ogendo, (2001) reported a significant increase in dry biomass yield of haricot bean by rhizobium inoculation.

Table 24:-Effect of Rhizobium Inoculation and VC application on yield and yield components of Haricot bean

		AGDB (kg ha ⁻¹)	Grain yield(kg ha ⁻¹)	Straw (kg ha ⁻¹)	HI
Rhizobium	Inoculated	3509 ^a	1855 ^a	1654	52.81
	Non-inoculated	3311 ^b	1724 ^b	1587	51.91
LSD		1.1656	0.6418	NS	NS
P value		0.0002	0.0001	0.0732	0.1872
P rate (kg ha⁻¹)	0	3101 ^c	1595 ^c	1513 ^c	51.50 ^b
	30	3763 ^a	2021 ^a	1723 ^a	53.84 ^a
	60	3364 ^b	1752 ^b	1623 ^b	52.04 ^b
	LSD	0.7053	0.3883	0.4051	0.6513
P value		<.0001	<.0001	<.0001	0.0153
VC rate (t ha⁻¹)	0	3192 ^c	1659 ^c	1545 ^b	51.84
	2.5	3352 ^b	1757 ^b	1582 ^b	52.57
	5	3684 ^a	1952 ^a	1732 ^a	52.96
	LSD	1.1661	0.667	0.9231	NS
P value		<.0001	<.0001	0.0004	0.3847
CV (%)		5.05	5.55	8.41	4.73

Mean values within a columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at $P \leq 0.05$; NS= non-significant; CV= Coefficient of variation; VC=vermicompost; AGDB=above ground dry biomass

According to the result of this experiment, application of 30kg ha⁻¹ P resulted in the highest (3763 kg ha⁻¹) yield of haricot bean dry biomass followed by the application rate of 60kg ha⁻¹ which is 3364 kg ha⁻¹, while the lowest dry biomass was recorded from the control. In agreement with this result, Gidago *et al.*, (2011) and Paulos. (2018) stated that application rate of phosphorus could boost above-ground dry biomass of haricot bean. In addition, the reduction of dry biomass as the level of phosphorus increased was also observed on those experiments. Unlike the finding of this experiment, Ezekiel *et al.*, (2010) reported a non-significant yield response of soya bean dry biomass. The biomass increment of haricot beans with the application

rate of phosphorus fertilizer might be due to the function of phosphorus in increasing leaf number, leaf area, and number of branches per plant. Besides, plants that receive an adequate amount of P might increase photosynthetic area and the number of pods per plant, which leads to more bean production.

The application rate of 5t ha⁻¹ VC resulted in a higher (3684kg ha⁻¹) value of dry biomass while the lowest dry biomass (3192 kg ha⁻¹) was recorded from the control. This result was in agreement with that of (Najar et al, 2015) report on the effect of vermicompost on the productivity of plants. The increasing effect of VC on the dry biomass of haricot bean might be due to its capability to stimulate the growth and yield of crops (Suthar, 2009) due to the presence of humic acids in VC, which play an important role in plant metabolism through their involvement in cell respiration, photosynthesis, oxidative phosphorylation, protein synthesis, and various enzymatic reactions.

Table 25: Interaction effect of Rhizobium Inoculation with phosphorus on yield of Haricot bean

P rate(kg ha ⁻¹)	Above ground dry biomass (Kg ha ⁻¹)		Grain yield(kgha-1)	
	Inoculated	Non-inoculated	Inoculated	Non-inoculated
0	3095 ^c	3106 ^c	1601 ^c	1582 ^c
30	3954 ^a	3572 ^b	2128 ^a	1914 ^b
60	3478 ^b	3250 ^c	1829 ^b	1675 ^c
LSD (< 0.05)	1.6492		0.9433	
RH*P	0.0061		0.0222	
CV (%)	5.05		5.5	

Mean values within a columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at P≤0.05; CV= Coefficient of variation;

The interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with 30kg ha⁻¹ Prate obtained the highest amount of above-ground dry biomass 3905kg ha⁻¹ with 20.36% biomass yield increment from the control. In line with this result, (Abbasi *et al.*, 2010), reported that the interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with the phosphorus rate of application significantly increased dry biomass and yield production of soybean. The increasing effect of biomass by the interaction

effect of inoculation with P application might be due to the function of phosphorus for the energy transformation in nodules of legume crops (Hussain, 2017), This implies that phosphorus application helps to improve nodulation and N₂-fixation which is important for the addition of more nitrogen from fixation for crop growth and yield improvement.

The application rate of phosphorus with VC application rate significantly affects the dry biomass of haricot bean. The interaction effect of 30kg ha⁻¹ P with 5t ha⁻¹ VC (33.85%) resulted in yield increment over the control, with their respective yields of 3971 kg ha⁻¹ and 2627kg ha⁻¹. This result is supported by (Debela *et al.*,2021), statement on the significant effect of integrated application of rhizobium and NPS fertilization on the biomass yield of soya bean at Bako western Ethiopia. The integrated effect of vermicompost and phosphorus improves the number of leaves, branches, and pods per plant; similarly, seed number and HSW are increased, thus the enhancement of those yield components boasts biomass yield of haricot bean. The function of phosphorus in enhancing the growth and pod-setting processes of haricot bean influences the dry biomass of haricot bean (Gabisa *et al.*, 2017). Concurrently, vermicompost application promotes the growth and yield of plants due to its outstanding character in increasing the essential nutrients in the soil and promoting the growth of plants. The application of vermicompost to the soil provides a suitable medium for plants and leads to an increase in shoot biomass (Blouin *et al.*, 2019).

4.5.5. Grain yield

The main effects (rhizobium inoculation, phosphorus rate and VC application) and the two way interaction (phosphorus rate and VC application) very highly significantly affects grain yield of haricot bean, also the two way interaction effect (rhizobium inoculation with phosphorus rate and rhizobium inoculation with VC application), However, the three way interaction effect was non-significant in this parameter.

The interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with 30kg ha⁻¹ P and 60kg ha⁻¹ P application rate results 24.34% higher value, compared to the control treatment with its highest haricot bean yield (2128kg ha⁻¹), while the lowest grain yield (1601kg ha⁻¹) was obtained from the control treatment. This result agreed with the finding of Belete *et al.*, (2019) who reported higher result of haricot bean yield due to the interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with phosphorus

application compared with the single use of phosphorus or Rhizobia inoculation alone. increase in the grain yield as result of main effect of strain and P fertilizer might be due to better performing of phosphorus, which plays a role in healthy plant growth, contributing to structural strength, crop quality, and seed production (Chimdi et al., 2022). N₂-fixing legumes with sufficient phosphorus did grow well and they will be more active than inadequate phosphorus application, this might be because nitrogen fixation by bacteria, ammonium uptake by amino acids, and cellular ureites in nodules are insufficient to support plant growth. Similarly Bekele and Hailemariam, (2021) reported non-significant yield response of soya bean by the interaction effect of rhizobium with phosphorus and similarly the report showed higher seed yield due to inoculation, similar to the finding of this experiment.

Table 26: Interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with VC application on grain yield of haricot bean

Grain yield(kgha-1)		
VC rate(t ha-1)	Inoculated	Non-inoculated
0	1748 ^c	1569 ^d
2.5	1774 ^c	1757 ^c
5	2043 ^a	1862 ^b
LSD (< 0.05)	0.5248	
RH*VC	0.0488	
CV (%)	6.9	

Mean values within a columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at $P \leq 0.05$; CV= Coefficient of variation; VC=vermicompost;

The combined application of rhizobium inoculation with VC rate results the highest grain yield unlike to the interaction of VC rate and without inoculation, this result indicates that the interaction effect of vermicompost with rhizobium positively increase haricot bean yield ,there for the highest yield of haricot bean (2043kg ha⁻¹) was obtained from the combination effect of rhizobium inoculation with 5t ha⁻¹ VC ,while the lowest grain yield (1569kg ha⁻¹) was obtained from the control treatment. The combination effect of inoculation and VC increase yield of legumes due to the beneficial effect of vermicompost which mainly attributed in increasing N₂-fixation through root growth and nodulation (Debela *et al.*,2021), nitrogen availability increases growth and leaf area index of plant which in turn enhances absorption of light leads to increase dry matter and yield of legumes (Togay *et al.*, 2008).This result agreed with that of Alkobaisy and Mutlag, (2021),experimental finding on significant increment of mung bean grain yield, due

to the interaction effect of rhizobium with vermicompost, contrary to this result, Nawaz *et al.*, (2017) who found non-significant value of chick pea by the interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with FYM ,however there report shows higher yield of chick pea from interaction effect compared to control treatment.

Table 27: Interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with VC application on grain yield of haricot bean

P rate(kgha ⁻¹)	Above ground dry biomass(Kg ha ⁻¹)			Grain yield(Kg ha ⁻¹)		
	VC rate(t ha ⁻¹)			VC rate(t ha ⁻¹)		
	0	2.5	5	0	2.5	5
0	2627 ^e	3170 ^d	3505 ^c	1302 ^e	1645 ^d	1839 ^c
30	3722 ^b	3596 ^{bc}	3971 ^a	1996 ^b	1923 ^{bc}	21.5 ^a
60	3229 ^d	3289 ^d	3575 ^{bc}	1679 ^d	1705 ^d	1872 ^c
LSD (< 0.05)	2.0198			1.1553		
P*VC	0.0001			<.0001		
CV (%)	5.05			5.5		

Mean values within a columns followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at P≤0.05; CV= Coefficient of variation; VC=vermicompost;

Interaction effect of phosphorus rate and VC application improves the yield of haricot bean according to the result of this experiment. The highest (2145kg ha⁻¹) grain yield of haricot bean was recorded from the interaction effect of 30kg ha⁻¹ P and 5tha⁻¹ while the lowest (1302kg ha⁻¹) grain yield was found from control, as well this result shows 39.03% higher value over the control. This result was supported by the experimental finding of Arsalan *et al.*, (2016), who reported the significant effect of phosphorus rate and VC application on the grain yield of mung bean, likewise a statement by Alam *et al.*, (2013) illustrates the significant yield increment of rice due to the interaction effect of phosphorus with VC. Vermicompost application significantly increases the grain yields of legumes (Ebrahim, 2012), this might be due to the activity of humic acids which is found in VC (Ravimycin, 2016). Humic acids are molecules that regulate macro and micronutrient adsorption and metabolism which influence protein synthesis in the processes of plant growth as well the function of VC in stimulation of root growth by proliferation of root hair, increasing root biomass; enhancing plant growth and development contributes in higher yield of plants (Joshi *et al.*,2013). Yield of haricot bean results significant improvement due to different level of phosphorus application. (Paulos *et al.*, 2018) and (Gidago *et al.*, 2011). The

increasing effect of grain yield due to P application might be due to the phosphorus role on cell division and in the growth of new tissue, consequently there might more branch number which can hold more leaf number that feed seeds of the plant through photosynthesis and mostly but not always as the number of branch increase number of pods also increase (Zebire and Gelgelo, 2019). According to the result of this experiment, application rate of 30 kg ha⁻¹ P shows higher result of haricot bean yield and yield components over the application rate of 60kg ha⁻¹ P. This might be because this higher rate of phosphorus is above the optimum level in the soil and it may interrupt the availability of other nutrients, which in turn can bring reduction in growth of bean. Similar to this finding, Turuko and Mohamme, (2014) reported the reduction of grain yield due to the application rate of phosphorus above 30kg ha⁻¹.

4.5.6. Straw yield

Straws are one of the major agricultural products which have many uses within the farm economy, serving as essential to soil fertility ingredient, when it is discomposed in to the soil as manure, can be included as component of compost preparation and livestock fodder are some of the major function (Capper, 1990).

The main effects (phosphorus rate and VC application) very highly significantly affect straw yield, while the main effect rhizobium inoculation and the interaction effects was non-significant. Application rate of 5t ha⁻¹ VC obtains the highest straw yield 1732kg ha⁻¹ while the application rate of 60kg ha⁻¹P and the control treatment are similar statistically, with their respective value 1545kg ha⁻¹ and 1582kgha⁻¹.The highest straw yield following vermicompost application may be attributable to the function of vermicompost in the formation of organic acids, stimulation of the efficiency of the beneficial microorganisms, and lowering of the soil pH; all of these factors will increase the dissolution of the compounds of the fixed or precipitating elements and thereby increase their availability in the soil and the plant (Sinha *et al.*, 2009).The highest straw yield 1723kg ha⁻¹ was obtained from the application rate of 30kg ha⁻¹ while the lowest 1513kg ha⁻¹ straw yield was obtained from the control treatment, similarly Birhanu, (2020) reported the significant effect of vermicompost and phosphorus application on straw yield.

4.5.7. Harvest index (%)

Harvest index was only significantly ($P=0.0153$) affected by phosphorus rate, while rhizobium, VC application inoculation and the interaction effects was non-significant in this parameter. The highest (53.84%) HI was obtained from the application rate of $30\text{kg ha}^{-1}\text{P}$, while the control results the lowest (51.50) HI. Similar to the result of this experiment significant increment of HI were reported by Chimdi et al., (2022), due to the application rate of phosphorus, contrary to this Dejene et al., (2016) reported non-significant result of HI on common bean due to phosphorus application rate. The increase in the harvest index might be due to the highest grain yield due to phosphorus application effect on the enhancement of pod and seed number.

4.6. Pearson correlation coefficients among some haricot bean growth and yield parameters and rhizobium and vermicompost application

Correlation measures the statistical relationship or association between two continuous variables and gives information about the magnitude of the association as well as the direction of the relationship (Schober and Schwarte, 2018). The correlation analysis of the results indicated both positive and negative relationships between soil chemical properties, growth, and yield parameters of haricot beans. Positive and significant relation was observed between soil-available phosphorus and %Ndfa ($r = 0.42^{**}$), this might be because nitrogen-fixing bacteria use available phosphorus to fix atmospheric N_2 , as their energy source. There by the increasing amount of available phosphorus in the soil thorough fertilization and VC application positively influence BNF. %Ndfa has a highly significant and positive correlation with total soil nitrogen ($r = 0.50^{***}$), percent of soil OM ($r = 0.44^{***}$), and branch number ($r = 0.60^{***}$) (Appendix table: 2). This outcome implies the positive effect of BNF from atmospheric N_2 fixation on the increasing percent of total soil nitrogen because BNF is the association of microorganisms and legume plants in which microorganisms obtain food and energy from the plant, while the plant utilizes the N produced by microorganisms for its growth and development, therefore the plant consumes much less N_2 from the soil, in addition, nitrogen-fixing plants accumulate the fixed N_2 in their roots, stems, and leaves, and when they finish their life cycle, they will be decomposed into the soil and there will be nitrogen accumulation in the soil (Sharma *et al.*, 2023). %Ndfa also shows a highly significant and positive relation with pod number

($r=0.79^{***}$), grain yield ($r = 0.88^{***}$), and above-ground dry biomass (0.87^{***}), as well %Ndfa shows strong relation with those haricot bean yield parameters. The result of this analysis shows that %Ndfa through inoculation of Rhizobium phosphorus rate and VC application positively influences soil total nitrogen growth and yield of haricot bean by providing additional nitrogen for the plant in addition to soil and vermicompost nitrogen. The soil chemical parameters TN ($r = 0.43^{**}$), OM ($r = 0.45^{***}$), and CEC ($r = 0.61^{***}$) were positively and highly significantly correlated with grain yield, which means that increasing the level of plant essential nutrient through N_2 -fixation and enhancing soil nutrients and soil cation exchange site through organic amendment like VC application could increase positively the yield of haricot bean.

4.7. Economic profitability

Economic analysis entails the evaluation of costs and benefits and allows assessing the impact of a change in the production system on a farmer's net income (Cabrillo, 2016). The gross field benefit of each treatment was computed by multiplying the field or farm gate price of the grain yield of haricot bean at the study area for one hectare of yield production, i.e., the price of grain yield was considered the same price. The price of grain yield (40 ETB per kg) was determined following the average price of haricot bean at the local market.

The total variable cost of rhizobium, phosphorus, and VC is considered a variable cost, and the costs of production practices such as labor costs (for field preparation, sowing, weeding, and harvesting), management, seed costs were considered to remain the same or would be insignificant among treatments. The cost of VC was adjusted based on home preparation, in which the cost of 1 kg of vermi worm was 500 ETB from local worm producers, and composting bed preparation and the general vermicompost preparation cost were included as variable costs. Accordingly, the highest variable cost of 31,852 (ETB) was recorded from the treatment rhizobium inoculation with 60kg ha^{-1} P and 5 t ha^{-1} VC application rate, while the lowest variable cost of 11,712 (ETB ha^{-1}) was recorded from 0kg ha^{-1} P with non-rhizobium inoculation.

Table 28:-Rhizobium inoculation, phosphorus rate and VC application effect on the Economic profitability

Rhizobium	VC rate(t ha⁻¹)	Phosphorus (kg ha⁻¹)	AvGY	AGY (kg ha⁻¹)	GBV (ETB kg ha⁻¹)	TVC (ETB)	NBV (ETB)	MRR
Non-inoculated	0	0	1219.33	1097.4	43,896	11,712	32,184	-
Non-inoculated	0	30	1888	1699.2	67,968	16,962	51,006	358.51
Non-inoculated	0	60	1601.67	1441.5	57,660	26,712	30,948	D
Non-inoculated	2.5	0	1714	1542.6	61,704	14,212	47,492	D
Non-inoculated	2.5	30	1873.33	1686	67,440	19,462	47,978	9.26
Non-inoculated	2.5	60	1634.33	1470.9	58,836	29,212	29,624	D
Non-inoculated	5	0	1814	1632.6	65,304	16,212	49,092	D
Non-inoculated	5	30	1981.67	1783.5	71,340	21,462	49,878	14.97
Non-inoculated	5	60	1789	1610.1	64,404	31,212	33,192	D
Inoculated	0	0	1385.33	1246.8	49,872	12,352	37,520	D
Inoculated	0	30	2103.33	1893	75,720	17,602	58,118	392.34
Inoculated	0	60	1756.33	1580.7	63,228	27,352	35,876	D
Inoculated	2.5	0	1575.67	1418.1	56,724	14,852	41,872	D
Inoculated	2.5	30	1972.33	1775.1	71,004	20,102	50,902	172
Inoculated	2.5	60	1774.67	1597.2	63,888	29,852	34,036	D
Inoculated	5	0	1864	1677.6	67,104	16,852	50,252	D
Inoculated	5	30	2308	2077.2	83,088	22,102	60,986	204.46
Inoculated	5	60	1955.67	1760.1	70,404	31,852	38,552	D

Where, AvGY=average grain yield; AGY=adjusted grain yield, GBV=growth benefit value, TVC=Total variable cost; NBV=Net benefit value; MRR=Marginal rate of return; ETB=Ethiopian Birr (currency); cost of TSP (1kg) fertilizer =35 ETB birr; cost of one Pac (125g) rhizobium= 160 ETB birr

The economic results of rhizobium, phosphorus, and VC effects showed that all treatments were economically feasible, as the net benefit values (NBV) were greater than zero ($NBV > 0$) (Table 28). The highest ($60,986 \text{ ETB ha}^{-1}$) net benefit value was obtained from rhizobium inoculation with the application of $30 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}\text{P}$ and 5 t ha^{-1} , with the MRR of 204.46%, while the lowest ($29,624 \text{ ETB ha}^{-1}$) was from $60 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}\text{P}$ rate and 2.5 t ha^{-1} application with non-rhizobium inoculation, followed by the application of rhizobium inoculation with $30 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}\text{P}$ and 0 t ha^{-1} vermicompost, which obtained $58,118 \text{ ETB ha}^{-1}$ net benefit value with the highest MRR of 392.34%. In agreement with this, Paulos *et al.*, (2018), reported the highest net benefit value from $26 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}\text{P}$ application, as well Sigaye *et al.*, (2020) also found an increasing rate of net benefit and MRR% as the application rate of phosphorus increased. In addition, Kenea and Gedamu, (2019) revealed that the increasing rate of VC application significantly increases the net benefit value of garlic production.

The minimum rate of return that farmers would consider acceptable in most situations was between 50% and 100%. The treatment with the highest net benefit, a relatively low variable cost, and an acceptable MRR becomes the tentative recommendation for treatments that are subject to the marginal rate of return, rather than the treatment with the highest marginal rate of return (CIMMYT, 1988). The results of non-dominated treatments indicated that for each one birr invested in the purchase and preparation of fertilizers, it was possible to recover one birr plus an extra 3.92 ha^{-1} and $2.05 \text{ birr ha}^{-1}$ as the fertilizer application changed from rhizobium inoculation with $0 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}\text{P}$ and $0 \text{ t ha}^{-1}\text{VC}$ interaction treatment to interaction effect inoculation with $30 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}\text{P}$ and $0 \text{ t ha}^{-1}\text{VC}$ and inoculation with $30 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}\text{P}$ and $5 \text{ t ha}^{-1}\text{VC}$, respectively. Therefore, the best economical treatment to be recommended was interaction effect inoculation with $30 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}\text{P}$ and $0 \text{ t ha}^{-1}\text{VC}$. However, based on the net benefit value, relatively lower cost of production, and the long-lasting positive effect of vermicompost on soils, the interaction effect of inoculation with $30 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}\text{P}$ and $5 \text{ t ha}^{-1}\text{VC}$ can be an acceptable recommendation for farmers.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Poor agricultural land management is one of the major factors in declining soil fertility and crop productivity. Low soil fertility status and low fertilizer use are some of the major constraints limiting haricot bean growth and yield in the study area.

The highest fixed nitrogen (66.18 kg ha^{-1}) and %Ndfa (52.04%) were obtained due to the interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with $30 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ P}$, as well as the interaction effect of inoculation with $5 \text{ t ha}^{-1} \text{ VC}$ results in the highest total plant nitrogen ($118.09 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$) and fixed nitrogen (52.01 kg ha^{-1}). The highest amount of fixed nitrogen and %Ndfa (66.9 kg ha^{-1} and 52.46%) was obtained from interaction effect of phosphorus and VC application. Over all individual effects rhizobium inoculation, phosphorus and vermicompost application and there two-way interactions enhances the biological nitrogen fixation.

The results of soil moisture content at different haricot bean growth stages (30, 60, 90 days) results the highest (27.79%, 26.7%, and 19.44% respectively) due to the application rate of $5 \text{ t ha}^{-1} \text{ VC}$; in addition, soil chemical properties (TN, avail.P, %OC, CEC, Ca, Na, K) were significantly increased with their respective value (0.13%, 6.33 mg/kg), 1.52%, 13.11 cmol (+) kg^{-1} , 6.02 cmol (+) kg^{-1} , 10.73 cmol (+) kg^{-1} and 1.25 cmol (+) kg^{-1}), due to the application rate of $5 \text{ t ha}^{-1} \text{ VC}$. However, the interaction effect of inoculation with VC application shows the highest increasing impact on %OC(1.68%), Ca(6.38 cmol (+) kg^{-1}), Mg(0.65 cmol (+) kg^{-1}), Na(0.29 cmol (+) kg^{-1}), in addition, the highest 1.61% soil OC and available phosphorus (12.30 mg kg^{-1}) were obtained due to the interaction effect of 60 kg ha^{-1} with 5 t ha^{-1} application. In general the soil of the experimental site shows general nutrient improvement and soil moisture enrichment due to vermicompost application.

Growth and yield parameters of haricot beans were positively influenced by the rhizobium inoculation, phosphorus, and vermicompost application effect. Physiological parameters days to 50% and days to 90% maturity flowering were significantly affected due to the interaction effect of inoculation with VC application, and inoculation with phosphorus application due to the interaction effects of phosphorus and VC application. The highest plant height (50.67cm) LAI (2.83) and number of branches per plant (4.87), were recorded from the interaction effect of 5 t

ha⁻¹ VC application with 60kg ha⁻¹ P, 0kg ha⁻¹ P, and 30kg ha⁻¹ P respectively. The interaction effect of 5t ha⁻¹ with 30kg ha⁻¹ P results in significant influence on the yield components of haricot bean, the highest number of pods 19.60 per plant, above-ground dry biomass 3971 kg ha⁻¹ and grain yield 2145 kg ha⁻¹. In addition, the highest 2043 kg ha⁻¹ and 2100 kg ha⁻¹ grain yield of haricot bean in the study area was obtained from the interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with 5t ha⁻¹ VC application and rhizobium inoculation with 30kg ha⁻¹ P. Generally, rhizobium inoculation, 5t ha⁻¹ VC application, and 30kg ha⁻¹ P rate increase the growth and yield of haricot beans, according to the results of this experiment.

However, the interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation with phosphorus rate and VC application significantly affects days to 50% flowering, days to 90% physiological maturity, seed number, and HSW. The highest seed number (6.2) and HSW (29.83) were obtained from rhizobium inoculation with 30kg ha⁻¹ P and 5t ha⁻¹ VC, in addition, the highest net benefit (60,986 ETB ha⁻¹) from economic analysis was obtained due to this interaction effect. Overall, ensuring an optimum supply of rhizobium inoculation, phosphorus fertilization, and vermicompost application increased the grain yield of haricot bean by improving nitrogen fixation, optimizing soil moisture status, and enhancing soil fertility status. Therefore, application of rhizobium inoculation with 30 kg ha⁻¹ P and 5 t ha⁻¹ vermicompost is recommended due to its better performance on soil fertility, growth, yield, and economic return of haricot bean at Dore baffano.

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7. APPENDIX TABLE

Appendix 1: Effect of rhizobium, phosphorus and vermicompost rate on the selected chemical properties of soil

	TN (%)	P (mg/kg)	OC (%)	CEC cmol (+) kg-1	Ca cmol (+) kg-1	Mg cmol (+) kg-1	Na cmol (+) kg-1	K cmol (+) kg-1
Rhizobium Inoculated	0.12a	7.51a	1.50a	12.14a	5.9096	0.60a	0.26a	1.22a
Non-inoculated	0.11b	6.40b	1.28b	11.40b	5.6796	0.49b	0.23b	1.13b
LSD	0.0042	0.631	0.0425	0.5876	0.2293	0.0281	0.0152	0.04
P value	0.0205	0.0008	<.0001	0.0143	0.0493	<.0001	<.0001	0.0001
0	0.15	4.09c	1.38	11.72ab	5.76	0.57a	0.24	1.2
30	0.12	5.98b	1.37	12.35a	5.78	0.51b	0.24	1.18
60 (kg ha-1)	0.12	10.8a	1.42	11.24b	5.83	0.55a	0.25	1.15
LSD	NS	0.8187	NS	0.7196	NS	0.0345	NS	NS
P value	0.1091	<.0001	0.2422	0.0132	0.8664	0.0118	0.4107	0.0993
0	0.11b	3.23b	1.27c	10.58c	5.63b	0.5397	0.23b	1.11b
2.5	0.12b	6.25a	1.38b	11.75b	5.73ab	0.5378	0.25a	1.16b
5 (t ha-1)	0.13a	6.33a	1.52a	13.11a	6.02a	0.5578	0.25ab	1.25a
LSD	0.0051	0.7729	0.0521	0.7196	0.2808	NS	0.0186	0.0489
P value	<.0001	0.0001	<.0001	0.0001	0.0126	0.4041	0.0199	<.0001
CV (%)	6.44	16.4	5.53	9.03	7.15	9.34	10.73	3.63

Appendix 2:-Pearson correlation coefficient among some soil chemical properties, haricot bean growth and yield parameters.

	%OC	CEC	FN	%Ndfa	LAI	Branch	POD	SEED	HSW	ABG	grain yield
1											
0.522***	1										
0.404**	0.575***	1									
0.443***	0.602***	0.976***	1								
0.416**	0.277*	0.295*	0.345*	1							
0.553***	0.598***	0.622***	0.616***	0.179	1						
0.497***	0.438***	0.783***	0.791***	0.297*	0.663***	1					
0.423**	0.323*	0.51***	0.571***	0.332*	0.491***	0.510***	1				
0.115	0.395**	0.463***	0.434**	0.039	0.41**	0.353**	0.326*	1			
0.457***	0.615***	0.847***	0.872***	0.327*	0.676***	0.713***	0.598***	0.451***	1		
0.452***	0.609***	0.860***	0.888***	0.343*	0.623***	0.71***	0.629***	0.481***	0.953***	1	

	TN	avl.P
TN	1	
avl.P	-0.086	1
%OC	0.500***	0.094
CEC	0.568***	-0.32
FN	0.468***	0.3649**
%Ndfa	0.496***	0.4235**
LAI	0.16	0.089
Branch	0.503***	0.079
POD	0.456***	0.126
SEED	0.294*	0.395
HSW	0.395**	-0.12
ABG	0.431**	0.074
grain yield	0.4304**	0.059

Appendix.3:-Mean squares of ANOVA for growth and yield of haricot bean due to the effect of rhizobium inoculation and VC rate

	Rep	Rhizobium	VC	Phosphorus	RH*VC	RH*P	VC*P	RH*VC*P	Error	CV (%)
Degree of freedom	2	1	2	2	2	2	4	4	34	
Fixed Nitrogen kg/ha	47.86	1286.47***	1727.62***	4884***	86.29*	444.03***	67.22*	57.47ns	24.19	10.97
%Ndfa	1.39	433.39***	555.83***	1765.76***	36.76ns	87.47**	48.65*	13.36ns	12.76	8.59
Total plant Nitrogen	48.97	1278.67***	1851.85***	5923.06***	85.01*	441.56***	149.29***	57.46ns	24.22	4.77
Days to 50%flowering	0.17	0.30ns	16.22***	8.0***	4.96**	14.30***	5.72***	3.96**	0.91	2.04
Days to 90% maturity	0.02	25.35***	22.69***	1.13ns	3.02**	2.80*	9.52***	1.96*	0.57	1.48
Plant height	6.94	197.04***	230.23***	36.73*	4.87ns	7.47ns	20.82ns	10.776ns	9.6	6.65
branch number	0.02	0.92***	2.24***	0.47***	0.15ns	0.01ns	0.41***	0.05ns	0.05	5.31
leaf number	0.69	5.35*	6.35***	7.35***	0.80ns	0.80ns	1.44ns	0.16ns	0.72	5.81
LAI	0.02	1.053***	0.04ns	0.002ns	0.04ns	0.02ns	0.12*	0.05ns	0.03	6.64
Pod number	1.66	35.85***	39.30***	22.69***	4.22ns	3.75ns	11.38***	0.91ns	1.64	7.59
Seed per pod	0.01	1.5***	0.27**	1.31***	0.26**	0.81***	1.29***	0.15*	0.04	3.62
Hundred seed weight	0.34	0.004ns	6.15**	14.13***	9.58***	1.78ns	3.56**	3.67**	0.8	3.33
Dry biomass yield	8.4	53.78***	113.11***	200.09***	6.95ns	17.64**	23.62***	3.11ns	2.96	5.05
Grain yield	4.48	23.21***	40.04***	83.46***	3.21*	4.14*	9.28***	1.15ns	0.97	5.5
Straw yield	2.73	6.34ns	18.58***	25.24***	1.59ns	4.77ns	3.31ns	0.82ns	1.86	8.41
Harvest index	15.8	11.12ns	6.034ns	29.11*	7.94ns	1.59ns	4.09ns	2.72ns	6.14	4.73

*** Very highly significant (P< 0.001), ** highly significant (P< 0.05), Ns = non-significant difference; Df=degree of freedom

Appendix 4:- Mean squares of ANOVA for selected physico-chemical properties of soil due to the effect of rhizobium inoculation and VC application

	Rep	Rhizobium	VC	Phosphorus	RH*VC	RH*P	VC*P	RH*VC*P	Error	CV(%)
Df	2	1	2	2	2	2	4	4	34	
TN	0.00003	0.00034*	0.00096***	0.0001ns	0.00003ns	0.00004ns	0.00003ns	0.00007ns	0.00006ns	6.44
OC	0.0042	0.61***	0.27***	0.012ns	0.045**	0.001ns	0.018*	0.001ns	0.0059	5.53
CEC	0.047	5.45*	42.28***	10.12***	0.18ns	2.51ns	2.85*	0.18ns	1.04	8.49
P	5.2	16.78**	24.16***	215.45***	1.98ns	16.43***	14.50***	1.43ns	1.302	16.4
Ca	0.02	0.71*	0.86*	0.025ns	0.97ns	0.13ns	0.12ns	0.066ns	0.172	7.15
Mg	0.002	0.018***	0.004ns	0.0007*	0.0063**	0.001ns	0.002	0.0003ns	0.001	11.23
Na	0.001	0.11***	0.09*	0.013ns	0.007ns	0.034ns	0.007ns	0.001ns	0.005	6.14
K	0.001	0.08***	0.15***	0.00007ns	0.004ns	0.018***	0.004ns	0.008**	0.002	3.63
30 day mc	5.16	7.45ns	106.46***	9.53	0.52ns	0.23ns	6.81ns	0.82ns	5.41	10.02
60 day mc	0.66	0.85ns	121.81***	1.08	11.45**	0.88ns	2.42ns	0.68ns	1.57	5.1
90 day mc	5.49	6.93ns	86.49***	5.42	5.78ns	5.77ns	5.09ns	1.99ns	2.36	12.45

*** Very highly significant (P< 0.001), ** highly significant (P< 0.05), Ns = non-significant difference. VC = vermi-compost, MC-moisture content; Df =degree of fredome

Image 1: Field preparation and rhizobium inoculation of haricot bean seed.

Image 2: Field lay out and sowing

Image 3: Haricot bean growth stages

Image 4: Soil moisture data collection and haricot bean yield components collection

Image 5: yield data collection

